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Preventing Recalcitrant **O**rganic **M**obile Industrial chemicals for **C**ircular Economy in the soil-sediment-water **S**ystem

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D2.1 – Toolbox improved *in silico* models for identification of PMT properties

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Executive Summary

This deliverable provides a toolbox which is a summary of the *in silico* models that were improved, newly developed, and adopted in the PROMISCES project for predicting the physicochemical properties and aquatic toxicity of PFAS.

In the case of physicochemical parameters needed for modeling fate, transport, and exposure of Perfluoroalkyl and Polyfluoroalkyl Substances (PFAS) five Quantitative Structure-Property Relationship models were improved/developed/adopted. Two QSPR models that were available in the literature (for water solubility, S_w , and vapor pressure, VP) were adopted and improved for the purpose of prediction of those endpoints for PFAS evaluated in PROMISCES. Moreover, two completely new QSPR models to predict the octanol-water partition (K_{ow}) and bioconcentration factor (BCF) of PFAS were developed. For the developed models for S_w , VP, and K_{ow} , in light of the limited data availability, a new approach combining physics-based methods with data-driven models was proposed and applied. The QSPR model for melting point (MP) that is available in literature, was evaluated in terms of the possibility of applying it for PFAS. This yielded a positive result and the QSPR model was therefore chosen as a model to predict MP for the compounds evaluated in PROMISCES.

All details of the improved/developed/adopted in PROMISCES *in silico* models for predicting the physicochemical properties of PFAS are presented in the standardized QMRF ((Q)SAR Model Reporting Format). Datasets for the models are available on-line on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13330024>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382313>). The toolbox in which the models for physicochemical properties are implemented is available as a browser application under the domain: <https://physchempfas.streamlit.app/>.

For estimation of other environmentally relevant endpoints required in fate and transport modeling, i.e. Henry's Law, $\log K_{AW}$, $\log K_{OA}$, and $\log K_{OC}$ further calculations were performed using appropriate mathematical transformations and predictions from the predictive models (S_w , VP, $\log K_{ow}$). Predictions for all considered environmental endpoints for 71 PFAS defined for the analysis in the PROMISCES project were estimated and gathered.

An AI/ML-based model to predict the aquatic toxicity of organic compounds in general was developed and validated. The quantitative ML model is able to predict the aquatic toxicity of PFAS compounds for different species. The developed model predicted PFAS better after transfer learning, especially when equally weighting PFAS and non-PFAS to get better predictions for PFAS. The model will be made available as a GitHub application.

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List of Abbreviations

AI/ML = artificial intelligence/machine learning
BCF = Bioconcentration Factor
CCC_{EXT} = concordance correlation coefficient
CV = Cross Validation
EC50 = concentration affecting 50% of the population
EQC = Environmental Quality Criteria
k_H = Henry's Law coefficient
K_{AW} = Air-water partition coefficient
K_{OA} = Octanol-air partition coefficient
K_{OC} = Soil adsorption coefficient
LogK_{OW} = Octanol water partition
LC50 = lethal concentration affecting 50% of the population
ML = machine learning
MP = Melting Point
MPC = Maximum Permissible Concentration
NOEC = no observed effect level
OECD = Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development
PAF = Potentially Affected Fraction
PFAS = Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances
PFAO = Perfluorooctanoic acid
PFOS = Perfluorooctanesulfonic acid
PM = persistent and mobile compounds
PMT = persistent, mobile, and toxic compounds
Q²_{EXT} = external validation coefficient
QSAR = Quantitative Structure-Activity Relationships
QMRF = (Q)SAR Model Reporting Format
QSPR = Quantitative Structure-Property Relationships
R² = determination coefficient
RMSE = root mean square error
REACH = Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals
S_w = Water solubility
SMILES = Simplified Molecular-Input Line-Entry System
SSD = Species-Sensitivity Distributions
VP = Vapor pressure

1 Introduction

The innovative modelling approaches for modeling fate, transport, and exposure to PFAS planned within WP2 of the H2020 PROMISCES project require physicochemical properties as well as aquatic toxicity data of these compounds as input. The needed data can be searched normally in the literature/databases. However, in the case of PFAS, not for every compound of PROMISCES' interest such data exist. In this case, computational approaches such as Quantitative Structure-Property Relationships (QSPR modeling) and other machine learning (ML) techniques can be applied to fill in the data gaps. These methods assume that there is a relationship between the chemical structure of a compound and its properties. Therefore, having available experimental data for a certain group of PFAS and using appropriate computational algorithms, it is possible to predict a given property for other similar PFAS congeners, and thus makes it possible to assess the fate, transport, and exposure of a larger group of these compounds.

Deliverable 2.1. directly relates to the objective of Task 2.1 which is to develop *in silico* models and approaches for the identification of properties of persistent and mobile (PM) chemicals and their degradation products for use in fate and transport modeling and risk assessment.

To develop valuable predictive models, together with all WP2 partners a set of endpoints containing physicochemical properties as well as aquatic toxicity of PFAS/PMT compounds for further implementation in the fate and transport modeling and risk assessment was selected. In the next step, existing predictive models (i.e. models needing individual physicochemical properties) dedicated to PFAS were searched in the literature and evaluated. Available models were verified if they were scientifically valid and could be easily applied for the prediction of the properties of new compounds. Simultaneously the experimental data for particular endpoints for PFAS were collected and evaluated if they can be used for training and validation of the models. To extend the approach for PM substances to PMT chemicals, a similar approach was followed for developing *in silico* models for prediction of the aquatic toxicity of PFAS congeners. First of all, a literature search was performed to collect aquatic toxicity data and QSAR models for predicting the toxicity of PFAS congeners. Thereupon literature data were searched for as well as existing toxicity data. With the aim to integrate as many of the chemical properties that potentially the toxicity of organic chemicals, the search was extended to all organic chemicals for which toxicity data could be found. The dataset generated was subsequently used for developing generic models for prediction of the aquatic toxicity of organic chemicals to virtually any biological species. Thereupon, the specific set of PFAS toxicity data was used to develop AI/ML-based models for the prediction of PFAS toxicity.

This deliverable provides a summary of the *in silico* models that were improved, newly developed, and adopted in the PROMISCES project for predicting physicochemical properties and aquatic toxicity of PFAS, as well as estimated values for physicochemical parameters for 71 PFAS taking into account within the PROMISCES project.

2 In silico models for PMT identification

2.1 Physicochemical properties

The whole list of investigated physicochemical endpoints for which (i) the predictive models were improved, developed or adopted, or (ii) suitable calculations requiring inputs from predictive models were applied to estimate values endpoints for PFAS investigated in PROMISCES is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Predicted physicochemical endpoints needed for fate and transport modeling planned within PROMISCES.

No.	Endpoints	Units	Comment
1	Water solubility (S_w)	mg/L	Improved model
2	Vapor pressure (VP)	mmHg	Improved model
3	Octanol water partition ($\text{Log}K_{ow}$)	-	New model
5	Bioconcentration Factor (BCF)	L/kg	New model
4	Melting Point (MP)	°C	Adopted model
6	Henry's Law coefficient (k_H)	[mol · Pa ⁻¹ · m ⁻³]	Calculation based on improved/developed models
7	Air-water partition coefficient (K_{AW})	-	Calculation based on improved/developed models
8	Octanol-air partition coefficient (K_{OA})	-	Calculation based on improved/developed models
9	Soil adsorption coefficient (K_{OC})	-	Calculation based on improved/developed models

QSARLab improved two QSPR models that were available in literature (for water solubility, S_w and vapor pressure, VP)¹ and developed two completely new QSPR models to predict the octanol-water partition (K_{ow})² and bioconcentration factor (BCF)³ of PFAS. The QSPR model for melting point (MP)⁴ that is available in literature, was evaluated in terms of the possibility of applying it for PFAS. This yielded a positive result and the QSPR model was therefore chosen as a model to predict MP for the compounds evaluated in PROMISCES. The appropriate formulations of the above mentioned models are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Equations of the developed predictive models.

Endpoint	Model equation and statistics	References
Water solubility (S_w)	$\log S_w = 1.049 (\pm 0.178) - 1.981 (\pm 0.204) \times T(F..)F + 1.042 (\pm 0.204) \times \text{SIC1}$ $T(F..)F$ - sum of topological distances between F..F ($T(F..F)$) SIC1 - structural Information Content index (neighborhood symmetry of 1-order) $R^2 = 0.85$ $\text{RMSE}_c = 1.13$ $Q^2_{LOO} = 0.83$ $\text{RMSE}_{EXT} = 1.327$ $Q^2_{F1} = 0.71$ $Q^2_{F2} = 0.71$ $Q^2_{F3} = 0.79$	Publication: Sosnowska, A., Mudlaff, M., Gorb, L., Bulawska, N., Zdybel, S., Bakker, M., Peijnenburg, W., & Puzyn, T. (2024). Expanding the applicability domain of QSPRs for predicting water solubility and vapor pressure of PFAS. <i>Chemosphere</i> 340, (2023) 139965. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11446922 Model: Mudlaff, M. (2024). Datasets from deliverable 2.1. on the physicochemical properties of PFAS compounds [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13330024 Streamlit app: https://physchempfas.streamlit.app/

Table 2 : Equations of the developed predictive models (cont.).

Endpoint	Model equation and statistics	References
Vapor Pressure (VP)	$\log VP = -0.8314 (\pm 0.143) - 2.2117 (\pm 0.149) \times F03[C-F] - 0.2274 (\pm 0.180) \times nDB - 1.8076 (\pm 0.175) \times AAC$ F03[C-F] - Frequency of C – F at topological distance 3 AAC - Mean information index on atomic composition nDB - Number of double bonds $R^2 = 0.92$ $RMSE_C = 0.86$ $Q^2_{LOO} = 0.90$ $RMSE_{EXT} = 0.86$ $Q^2_{F1} = 0.91$ $Q^2_{F2} = 0.91$ $Q^2_{F3} = 0.92$	Sosnowska, A., Mudlaff, M., Gorb, L., Bulawska, N., Zdybel, S., Bakker, M., Peijnenburg, W., & Puzyn, T. (2024). Expanding the applicability domain of QSPRs for predicting water solubility and vapor pressure of PFAS. <i>Chemosphere</i> 340, (2023) 139965. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11446922 Model: Mudlaff, M. (2024). Datasets from deliverable 2.1. on the physicochemical properties of PFAS compounds [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13330024 Streamlit app: https://physchempfas.streamlit.app/
Octanol water partition (LogK _{ow})	$\log K_{ow} = 6.341 (\pm 0.097) + 1.639 (\pm 0.122) \times T(F..F) - 1.854 (\pm 0.122) \times gmin$ T(F..F) - sum of topological distances between F..F Gmin - minimum atom E-state value in a molecule $R^2 = 0.95$ $RMSE_C = 0.75$ $Q^2_{LOO} = 0.93$ $RMSE_{EXT} = 0.87$ $Q^2_{F1} = 0.92$ $Q^2_{F2} = 0.92$ $Q^2_{F3} = 0.93$	Mudlaff, M., Sosnowska, A., Grob, L., Bulawska, N., Jagiello, K., & Puzyn, T. (2024). Environmental impact of PFAS: Filling data gaps using theoretical quantum chemistry and QSPR modeling. <i>Environment International</i> , 185, (2024), 108568. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382313 Model: Mudlaff, M. (2024). Datasets from deliverable 2.1. on the physicochemical properties of PFAS compounds [Data set]. Zenodo. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13330024 Streamlit app: https://physchempfas.streamlit.app/
Bioconcentration Factor (BCF)	$\log BCF = 3.01 (\pm 0.141) + 1.78 (\pm 0.182) \times GATS2v - 0.7 (\pm 0.182) \times P_VSA_e_5 - 0.8 (\pm 0.169) \times E3m + 1.27 (\pm 0.163) \times nCp$ GATS2v—Geary autocorrelation of lag 2 weighted by van der Waals volume (2D – Autocorrelation) P_VSA_e_5—P_VSA-like on Sanderson electronegativity, bin 5 (2D – P_VSA_like descriptor) E3m—3rd component accessibility directional WHIM index / weighted by mass (3D – WHIM) nCp—number of terminal primary C(sp ³) (2D – Functional group counts) $R^2 = 0.92$ $RMSE_C = 0.58$ $Q^2_{LOO} = 0.88$ $RMSE_{EXT} = 0.72$ $Q^2_{F1} = 0.89$ $Q^2_{F2} = 0.89$ $Q^2_{F3} = 0.88$	Kowalska, D., Sosnowska, A. & Puzyn, T. Structure-property modeling of bioconcentration factor (BCF) for Per- and Polyfluoroalkyl Substances (PFAS). <i>Under revision step in Chemosphere</i> (2024). Model: will be public (code and datasets) on Zenodo after acceptance of the publication Streamlite app: the model will be implemented to the app after acceptance of the publication. https://physchempfas.streamlit.app/

Table 2: Equations of the developed predictive models (cont.)

Endpoint	Model equation and statistics	References
Melting Point (MP)	$MP = -209.04 (\pm 139.9) + 132.95 (\pm 22.63) \times ACC + 3.04 (\pm 0.97) \times F02[C-F] - 18.97 (\pm 7.98) \times C-013 + 209.04 (\pm 139.9) \times RBF$ <p>ACC - 'information indices' which characterizes mean information index on atomic composition F02[C-F] - frequency of C-F at topological distance 2 C-013 - carbon connected to at least three electronegative atoms (X) CRX3 RBF - rotatable bond fraction</p> $R^2 = 0.81$ $RMSE_C = 0.40$ $Q^2_{LOO} = 0.78$ $RMSE_{EXT} = 0.27$ $Q^2_{F1} = 0.83$ $Q^2_{F2} = 0.43$ $Q^2_{F3} = 0.93$	Bhatarai, B. <i>et al.</i> CADASTER QSPR Models for Predictions of Melting and Boiling Points of Perfluorinated Chemicals. <i>Mol. Inform.</i> 30 , 189–204 (2011).

For estimation of other environmentally relevant endpoints required in fate and transport modeling, i.e. Henry's Law, $\log K_{AW}$, $\log K_{OA}$, and $\log K_{OC}$ ^{5–8} further calculations were performed using predictions from the predictive models reported in Table 2 (S_w , VP, $\log K_{OW}$). The applied appropriate mathematical transformations are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: The formula applied for estimating the relevant physicochemical parameters

Endpoint	Mathematical transformation	References
Henry's Law (k_H)	$k_H = \frac{S_w}{VP \cdot M} [\text{mol} \cdot \text{Pa}^{-1} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}]$ <p>Where S_w is the solubility, V_p is the vapor pressure, and M is the molar mass of the individual compound. The solubility was determined in units (mg/L) at 298 K, while the vapor pressure was in units of mmHg. To ensure consistency of units so that they agreed with the SI system proposed with the IUPAC recommendations, we recalculated the data accordingly.</p>	R. Sander: Compilation of Henry's law constants (version 4.0) for water as solvent, <i>Atmos. Chem. Phys.</i> , 15 , 4399–4981 (2015), doi:10.5194/acp-15-4399-2015.
Air–water partition coefficient (K_{AW})	$K_{AW} = \frac{k_H}{R \cdot T}$ <p>Where k_H is Henry's Law, R – gas constant (8.31 J mol⁻¹ · K⁻¹), and T - temperature (298.15 K). K_{AW} value is unitless. In the final step, all the values were logarithmized.</p>	Jönsson, J. Å., Vejrosta, J. & Novák, J. Air/water partition coefficients for normal alkanes (n-pentane to n-nonane). <i>Fluid Phase Equilibria</i> 9 , 279–286 (1982).
Octanol – air partition coefficient (K_{OA})	$K_{OA} = \frac{K_{OW}}{K_{AW}}$ <p>The K_{OA} was estimated by dividing the predicted K_{OW} by the calculated K_{AW} values. The values are logged at the end. The final K_{OA} results were assumed unitless.</p>	Xu, S. & Kropscott, B. Evaluation of the three-phase equilibrium method for measuring temperature dependence of internally consistent partition coefficients (KOW, KOA, and KAW) for volatile methylsiloxanes and trimethylsilanol. <i>Environ. Toxicol. Chem.</i> 33 , 2702–2710 (2014).

Table 3: The formula applied for estimating the relevant physicochemical parameters (cont.)

Endpoint	Mathematical transformation	References
Soil adsorption coefficient (K _{oc})	$\log K_{oc} = 0.00028 + (0.983 \cdot \log K_{ow})$ The Di Toro equation was used for non-volatile and semi-volatile organic compounds, respectively. The logK _{ow} model provided by QSPR was used.	Toro, D. M. D. A particle interaction model of reversible organic chemical sorption. <i>Chemosphere</i> 14 , 1503–1538 (1985).

All predictive models obtained within PROMISCES for physicochemical properties were developed using Python 3.⁹ and sklearn package.¹⁰ The descriptors used in the equations were calculated in the AlvaDesc program¹¹ using SMILES codes for all compounds. Owing to the lack or small amount of data to generate the values of water solubility, vapor pressure, and n-octanol water partition coefficient, the values used to train the models were simulated using COSMO-RS.¹²

The quality of the QSPR models was verified using appropriate metrics such as coefficients of determination (R²) and root mean squared error (RMSE_{cv}). An appropriate 1:X data split was also applied to each model. To verify the predictive ability, external validation was performed on the validation sets using mainly Q²_{EXT} (Q²_{F1, F2, F3}) coefficients, root mean square error RMSE_{EXT}, and concordance correlation coefficient CCC_{EXT}. The applicability domain of the obtained models was verified by presenting a graphical representation of the standardized residuals from leverage, known as Williams Plot.¹³ All improved/developed/adopted in PROMISCES *in silico* models^{1,2,3,4} are presented here in QMRF ((Q)SAR Model Reporting Format) which describes key information on QSAR models, including the results of the validation studies, described also below.

The final QSPR models are/will be published in open-access journals and will be made publically available on Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/communities/promisces/>).

The models, along with available data on the datasets used to create the models (training and validation sets), can be found on the Zenodo platform (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13330024>) in the PROMISCES community. The data has been used for the following endpoints: water solubility, vapor pressure, logP, melting point, and bioconcentration factor.

In addition, deliverable D2.1 has developed a toolbox that allows the prediction of solubility, logP, and vapor pressure values for PFAS compounds. The application, equipped with implemented QSAR-MLR models, allows users to predict and visualize the aforementioned properties by entering calculated descriptors generated by the widely available Ochem software. The model for prediction BCF will be also implemented in the streamlite app, after acceptance of the manuscript in Chemosphere. The application is free and available online at <https://physchempfas.streamlit.app/>.

The proper QSPR model used for prediction should follow the golden standards established for QSAR models within OECD in 2004.¹⁴ In accordance with these rules “to facilitate the consideration of a (Q)SAR model for regulatory purposes, it should be associated with the following information:

1. a defined endpoint;
2. an unambiguous algorithm;
3. a defined domain of applicability;
4. appropriate measures of goodness-of-fit, robustness, and predictivity;
5. a mechanistic interpretation, if possible.”¹⁵

Only models which fulfill all the above-mentioned requirements should be used for predicting biological activity / physical parameters of the substance. One of the unified formats of QSPR models reporting is the QMRF ((Q)SAR Model Reporting Format) proposed in 2007.¹⁶ This document format describes the summary and reporting of key information on QSAR models, including the results of the validation studies. The information is organized according to the OECD validation principles.

Below, all details of the improved/developed/adopted in PROMISCES *in silico* models for predicting physicochemical properties of PFAS are presented. Each predictive model is presented in QMRF format containing the information needed for repeating and applying the model for prediction of water solubility (S_w), vapor pressure (VP), octanol water partition ($\text{Log}K_{ow}$), bioconcentration factor (BCF), and melting point (MP) for PFAS-like compounds. Each QMRF is divided into 10 sections, which refer to different aspects of QSPR models:

Section 1 (QSAR identifier) is related to the description of the model, where the title, other related models, and software coding of the model is indicated.

Section 2 (General Information) provides general information about the developed model, e.g., the date and authors who prepared of QMRF, as well as the authors of the model and referring publication, available information of the model (e.g. training and external validation sets, source code, and algorithm) and information if there exist other QMRF documents for the exact model.

Section 3 (Defining the endpoint – OECD Principle 1) specifies the endpoint and units for the endpoint, the experimental protocol followed by the collection of the experimental sets, as well as the information on the data quality assessment and the relationship of the modeled (dependent variable) and measured endpoint (e.g. transformation, etc.).

Section 4 (Defining the algorithm – OECD Principle 2) refers to the type of the model (e.g. SAR, QSAR, Expert-based Systems, Neural Networks) and all information connected with the developed relationship. Here the information on used in the model descriptors, how they were estimated, how the selection of the descriptors was performed, and what is the ratio of the descriptors used in the model to chemicals in the training set are indicated. Moreover, the method and software used to derive algorithm is specified.

Section 5 (Defining the applicability domain – OECD Principle 3) provides detailed information about the chemical space in which the model predicts properly. Here the method of defining the applicability domain, as well as its limitations is mentioned.

Section 6 (Defining goodness-of-fit and robustness – OECD Principle 4) contains notes about the statistical analysis that should be performed to establish the performance of the model, consisting also of the internal validation (i.e., measures of goodness-of-fit and robustness). In this section, the information about the availability of the training set, the descriptors values for chemicals are included. All statistics describing the goodness-of-fit and robustness are reported.

Section 7 (Defining predictivity – OECD Principle 4) is associated with external validation of the model and determination of the predictive power of the model. In this section the information about the availability of the validation set, data for each descriptor and dependent variable for the external validation set as well as the information on how the validation set was defined (e.g., randomly, using a specific algorithm, searching in literature, etc.) are presented. Moreover, all statistics obtained by external validation, as well as predictivity assessment are indicated.

Section 8 (Providing the mechanistic interpretation – OECD Principle 5) refers to the mechanistic interpretation of the presented model. Here, information on the mechanistic basis of the model are

included. The description of the structural features that are responsible for the modeled property are demonstrated and the physicochemical interpretation of the used descriptors is explained.

Section 9 (Miscellaneous information) includes any other relevant and useful comments not indicated above, a bibliography (references not strictly associated with the developed model), and supporting information (if it is attached to the QMRF – supporting information may include the training and test sets submitted in defined file formats).

Section 10 (Summary for the JRC QSAR Model Database)¹⁷ is a summary section specified for the JRC Database. Here the QMRF number is generated as well as the publication date, keywords, and comments relevant to the publication of the QMRF in the JRC Database (e.g., updates) should be reported.

2.1.1 QMRF for a predictive model for water solubility (SW)

1. QSAR identifier

1.1. QSAR identifier (title):

QSPR model for predicting water solubility of PFAS compounds

1.2. Other related models:

Bhatarai, B. & Gramatica, P. Prediction of Aqueous Solubility, Vapor Pressure and Critical Micelle Concentration for Aquatic Partitioning of Perfluorinated Chemicals. *Environ Sci Technol* 45, 8120–8128 (2011).

1.3. Software coding the model:

Python 3.9.7.

2. General information

2.1. Date of QMRF:

January 2023

2.2. QMRF author(s) and contact details:

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2.3. Date of QMRF update(s):

N/A

2.4. QMRF update(s):

N/A

2.5. Model developer(s) and contact details:

1. M. Mudlaff, QSAR Lab Ltd, m.mudlaff@qsarlab.com

2. N. Buławska, QSAR Lab Ltd, n.bulawska@qsarlab.com

2.6. Date of model development and/or publication:

Published in 2023

2.7. Reference(s) to main scientific papers and/or software package:

Sosnowska, A., Mudlaff, M., Gorb, L., Bulawska, N., Zdybel, S., Bakker, M., Peijnenburg, W., & Puzyn, T. (2024). Expanding the applicability domain of QSPRs for predicting water solubility and vapor pressure of PFAS. *Chemosphere* 340, (2023) 139965. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11446922>

Bhatarai, B. & Gramatica, P. Prediction of Aqueous Solubility, Vapor Pressure and Critical Micelle Concentration for Aquatic Partitioning of Perfluorinated Chemicals. *Environ Sci Technol* 45, 8120–8128 (2011).

AlvaDesc: Mauri, A. (2020). alvaDesc: A tool to calculate and analyze molecular descriptors and fingerprints. In *Ecotoxicological QSARs* (pp. 801-820). Humana, New York, NY.

Python: Van Rossum, G., & Drake, F. L. (2009). *Python 3 Reference Manual*. Scotts Valley, CA: CreateSpace.

COSMO-RS: AMS 2022.1 COSMO-RS, SCM, Theoretical Chemistry, Vrije Universiteit, Amsterdam, The Netherlands. (2022).

2.8. Availability of information about the model:

The set of 56 PFAS compounds were selected to model development. Model was obtained based on two theoretical molecular descriptors (T(F..F) and SIC1). Structures, names, acronyms, CAS numbers, and SMILES of PFAS examined in this study are listed in a Supplementary Information 1. For the modeling, the multiple linear regression (MLR) approach was applied.

2.9. Availability of another QMRF for exactly the same model:

N/A

3. Defining the endpoint – OECD Principle 1

3.1. Species:

N/A

3.2. Endpoint:

Solubility

3.3. Comment on the endpoint:

Water solubility of PFAS compounds

3.4. Endpoint units:

log(mg/L)

3.5. Dependent variable:

Water solubility (S_w)

3.6. Experimental protocol:

Predictions were obtained according to Gaussian16 program. The impact of water mass has been considered as part of the COSMO approach. Solubility and vapor pressure were calculated using the COSMO-RS technique, which is included in the ADM software package. To obtain the physical properties, COSMO-RS treats polarization charge densities calculated in the COSMO-RS option of Gaussian16.

3.7. Endpoint data quality and variability:

Data were simulated for 89 compounds, where 10 compounds were rejected due to limitations of the program's computational capabilities. Calculated values were compared with experimental values based on their trend.

4. Defining the algorithm – OECD Principle 2

4.1. Type of model:

QSAR model - Multiple linear regression (MLR)

4.2. Explicit algorithm:

$$\log S_w = 1.049 (\pm 0.178) - 1.981 (\pm 0.204) \times T(F..F) + 1.042 (\pm 0.204) \times SIC1$$

4.3. Descriptors in the model:

T(F..) - sum of topological distances between F..F

SIC1 - structural Information Content index (neighborhood symmetry of 1-order)

4.4. Descriptor selection:

Descriptors of the model available in the literature were used. Structural and 2D atom pairs descriptors, which have an influence on the solubility were selected. Pairs of descriptors between which correlation did not exceed 0.6 were selected.

4.5. Algorithm and descriptor generation:

Descriptors of the model available in the literature were used. Where the compounds were drawn using Hyperchem software and their energy was minimized using the AM1 semiempirical method. Descriptors in the original literature model were calculated in dragon software. The obtained 0D-3D descriptors were selected using a genetic algorithm.

In this publication, the descriptors were calculated using SMILES notation in alvaDesc software. They belong to constitutional indices, topological indices, walk and path counts, and molecular properties. The number of descriptors has been first reduced by constant values and by descriptors with no data for at least one compound.

4.6. Software name and version for descriptor generation:

alvaDesc software

4.7. Chemicals/ Descriptors ratio:

56 chemicals / 2 descriptors

5. Defining the applicability domain – OECD Principle 3

5.1. Description of the applicability domain of the model:

Applicability domain was verified based on a plot of the standardized residuals versus the leverage values, so-called Williams plot. All compounds used in the training and validation sets should be

situated in the range of residuals differing by ± 3 standard deviations from the mean value. They should not also exceed the h^* value.

5.2. Method used to assess the applicability domain:

As it has been noted in section 5.1, the applicability domain of the model was assessed by the leverage approach, providing a cut-off hat value ($h^*=0.209$). The response applicability domain was also verified by the standardized residuals.

5.3. Software name and version for applicability domain assessment:

Williams plot was generated in Python 3.9.7.

5.4. Limits of applicability:

Two compounds (8:2 Fluorotelomer phosphate diester and perfluorooctadecanoic acid) was classified as outlier, because its leverage value was higher than h^* .

6. Defining goodness-of-fit and robustness – OECD Principle 4

6.1. Availability of the training set:

Yes

6.2. Availability information for the training set:

CAS RN: Yes

Chemical Name: Yes

Smiles: Yes

Formula: No

INChI: No

MOL file: No

6.3. Data for each descriptor variable for the training set:

All

6.4. Data for the dependent variable (response) for the training set:

All

6.5. Other information about the training set:

Dataset was split into training (T) and validation (V) sets by following the “1:Z algorithm”. Training set consist of 42 compounds.

6.6. Pre-processing of data before modelling:

Standard scaler - Standardize features by removing the mean and scaling to unit variance.

6.7. Statistics for goodness-of-fit:

$R^2 = 0.846$

$RMSE_C = 1.128$

$MAE_C = 0.845$

6.8. Robustness – Statistics obtained by leave-one-out cross validation:

$Q2_{LOO} = 0.826$

$RMSE_{CV} = 1.201$

$MAE_{CV} = 0.904$

6.9. Robustness – Statistics obtained by leave-many-out cross validation:

N/A

6.10. Robustness – Statistics obtained by Y-scrambling:

$R^2_{SCR} = 0.075$

6.11. Robustness – Statistics obtained by bootstrap:

N/A

6.12. Robustness – Statistics obtained by other methods:

N/A

7. Defining predictivity – OECD Principle 4

7.1. Availability of the external validation set:

Yes

7.2. Availability information for the external validation set:

CAS RN: Yes

Chemical Name:Yes

Smiles:Yes

Formula:No

INChI:No

MOL file:No

7.3. Data for each descriptor variable for the external validation set:

Yes

7.4. Data for the dependent variable (response) for the external validation set:

Yes

7.5. Other information about the external validation set:

Validation set consist of 14 compounds.

7.6. Experimental design of test set:

Every 4th compound in a group of chemicals, sorted by experimental values in ascending order, was assigned to the validation set.

7.7. Predictivity – Statistics obtained by external validation:

$$Q^2_{F1} = 0.714$$

$$Q^2_{F2} = 0.708$$

$$Q^2_{F3} = 0.787$$

$$RMSE_{EXT} = 1.327$$

$$MAE_{EXT} = 0.961$$

$$CCC_{EXT} = 0.827$$

7.8. Predictivity – Assessment of the external validation set:

Range of response for prediction set (n=14)

compounds:

S_w (log(mg/L)): -3.15/4.35 (range of correspondig training set: -8.15/4.11)

Range of modeling descriptors for prediction set (n=14)

compounds:

T(F..F): 6/2814 (range of corresponding training set: 6/6360)

SIC1: 0.22/0.70 (range of corresponding training set: 0.25/0.67)

7.9. Comments on the external validation of the model:

N/A

8. Providing a mechanistic interpretation – OECD Principle 5

8.1. Mechanistic basis of the model:

The model was developed by statistical approach. No mechanistic was defined a priori.

8.2. A priori or a posteriori mechanistic interpretation:

The original model published in Bhatarai B. and Gramatica P. [2]:

$$\log S_w = -0.418 (\pm 1.940) - 0.003 (\pm 0.001) T(F..F) + 5.185 (\pm 3.849) SIC1$$

New model with extended applicability domain (AD) using calculated value of S:

$$\log S_w = 1.049 (\pm 0.178) - 1.981 (\pm 0.204) \times T(F..F) + 1.042 (\pm 0.204) \times SIC1$$

T(F..F) - sum of topological distances between F..F

SIC1- structural Information Content index (neighborhood symmetry of 1-order)

The solubility of compounds belonging to the PFAS group decreases with the T(F..F) descriptor and increases with the SIC1 descriptor.

8.3. Other information about the mechanistic interpretation:

N/A

9. Miscellaneous information

9.1. Comments:

Scopes of expansion of the field:

The expansion of the AD increased the range of descriptors in the space. In the case of S, the domain changed from a minimum value by descriptor T(F..F) to 6 and a maximum value from 1146

to 6360, and by descriptor SIC1 from a minimum value expanded in the opposite direction from 0.26 to 0.22 and also from a maximum value from 0.67 to 0.7.

9.2. Bibliography:

1. Sosnowska, A., Mudlaff, M., Gorb, L., Bulawska, N., Zdybel, S., Bakker, M., Peijnenburg, W., & Puzyn, T. (2024). Expanding the applicability domain of QSPRs for predicting water solubility and vapor pressure of PFAS. *Chemosphere* 340, (2023) 139965. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11446922>

2. Bhatarai, B. & Gramatica, P. Prediction of Aqueous Solubility, Vapor Pressure and Critical Micelle Concentration for Aquatic Partitioning of Perfluorinated Chemicals. *Environ Sci Technol* 45, 8120–8128 (2011).

9.3. Supporting information:

10. Summary for the JRC QSAR Model Database (compiled by JRC)

10.1. **QMRF number:**

10.2. **Publication date:**

10.3. **Keywords:**

2.1.2 QMRF for a predictive model for vapor pressure (VP)

1. QSAR identifier

1.1. QSAR identifier (title):

QSPR model for predicting vapor pressure of PFAS compounds

1.2. Other related models:

Bhatarai, B. & Gramatica, P. Prediction of Aqueous Solubility, Vapor Pressure and Critical Micelle Concentration for Aquatic Partitioning of Perfluorinated Chemicals. *Environ Sci Technol* 45, 8120–8128 (2011).

1.3. Software coding the model:

Python 3.9.7.

2. General information

2.1. Date of QMRF:

January 2023

2.2. QMRF author(s) and contact details:

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80-172 Gdansk, Poland

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2.3. Date of QMRF update(s):

N/A

2.4. QMRF update(s):

N/A

2.5. Model developer(s) and contact details:

1. M. Mudlaff, QSAR Lab Ltd, m.mudlaff@qsarlab.com

2. N. Buławska, QSAR Lab Ltd, n.bulawska@qsarlab.com

2.6. Date of model development and/or publication:

Published in 2023

2.7. Reference(s) to main scientific papers and/or software package:

Sosnowska, A., Mudlaff, M., Gorb, L., Bulawska, N., Zdybel, S., Bakker, M., Peijnenburg, W., & Puzyn, T. (2024). Expanding the applicability domain of QSPRs for predicting water solubility and vapor pressure of PFAS. *Chemosphere* 340, (2023) 139965. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11446922>

Bhatarai, B. & Gramatica, P. Prediction of Aqueous Solubility, Vapor Pressure and Critical Micelle Concentration for Aquatic Partitioning of Perfluorinated Chemicals. *Environ Sci Technol* 45, 8120–8128 (2011).

AlvaDesc: Mauri, A. (2020). alvaDesc: A tool to calculate and analyze molecular descriptors and fingerprints. In *Ecotoxicological QSARs* (pp. 801-820). Humana, New York, NY.

Python: Van Rossum, G., & Drake, F. L. (2009). *Python 3 Reference Manual*. Scotts Valley, CA: CreateSpace.

COSMO-RS: AMS 2022.1 COSMO-RS, SCM, Theoretical Chemistry, Vrije Universiteit, Amsterdam, The Netherlands. (2022).

2.8. Availability of information about the model:

The set of 59 PFAS compounds were selected to model development. Model was obtained based on three theoretical molecular descriptors (F03[C-F], AAC and nDB). Structures, names, acronyms, CAS numbers, and SMILES of PFAS examined in this study are listed in a Supplementary Information

1. For the modeling, the multiple linear regression (MLR) approach was applied.

2.9. Availability of another QMRF for exactly the same model:

N/A

3. Defining the endpoint – OECD Principle 1

3.1. Species:

N/A

3.2. Endpoint:

Vapor pressure

3.3. Comment on the endpoint:

Vapor pressure of PFAS compounds

3.4. Endpoint units:

Log mmHg

3.5. Dependent variable:

Vapor pressure (VP)

3.6. Experimental protocol:

Predictions were obtained according to Gaussian16 program. The impact of water mass has been considered as part of the COSMO approach. Solubility and vapor pressure were calculated using the COSMO-RS technique, which is included in the ADM software package. To obtain the physical properties, COSMO-RS treats polarization charge densities calculated in the COSMO-RS option of Gaussian16.

3.7. Endpoint data quality and variability:

Data were simulated for 89 compounds, where 30 compounds were rejected due to limitations of the program's computational capabilities. Calculated values were compared with experimental values based on their trend.

4. Defining the algorithm – OECD Principle 2

4.1. Type of model:

QSAR model -Multiple linear regression (MLR)

4.2. Explicit algorithm:

$$\log VP = -0.8314 (\pm 0.143) - 2.2117 (\pm 0.149) \times F03[C-F] - 0.2274 (\pm 0.180) \times nDB - 1.8076 (\pm 0.175) \times AAC$$

4.3. Descriptors in the model:

Frequency of C – F at topological distance 3 (F03[C-F])

Mean information index on atomic composition (AAC)

Number of double bonds (nDB)

4.4. Descriptor selection:

Descriptors of the model available in the literature were used. Structural and 2D atom pairs descriptors, which have an influence on the solubility were selected. Pairs of descriptors between which correlation did not exceed 0.6 were selected.

4.5. Algorithm and descriptor generation:

Descriptors of the model available in the literature were used. Where the compounds were drawn using Hyperchem software and their energy was minimized using the AM1 semiempirical method. Descriptors in the original literature model were calculated in dragon software. The obtained 0D-3D descriptors were selected using a genetic algorithm.

In this publication, the descriptors were calculated using SMILES notation in alvaDesc software. They belong to constitutional indices, topological indices, walk and path counts, and molecular properties. The number of descriptors has been first reduced by constant values and by descriptors with no data for at least one compound.

4.6. Software name and version for descriptor generation:

alvaDesc software

4.7. Chemicals/ Descriptors ratio:

59 chemicals / 3 descriptors

5. Defining the applicability domain – OECD Principle 3

5.1. Description of the applicability domain of the model:

Applicability domain was verified based on a plot of the standardized residuals versus the leverage values, so-called Williams plot. All compounds used in the training and validation sets should be situated in the range of residuals differing by ± 3 standard deviations from the mean value. They should not also exceed the h^* value.

5.2. Method used to assess the applicability domain:

As it has been noted in section 5.1, the applicability domain of the model was assessed by the leverage approach, providing a cut-off hat value ($h^*=0.300$). The response applicability domain was also verified by the standardized residuals.

5.3. Software name and version for applicability domain assessment:

Williams plot was generated in Python 3.9.7.

5.4. Limits of applicability:

No compound was classified as outlier.

6. Defining goodness-of-fit and robustness – OECD Principle 4

6.1. Availability of the training set:

Yes

6.2. Availability information for the training set:

CAS RN:Yes

Chemical Name:Yes

Smiles:Yes

Formula:No

INChI:No

MOL file:No

6.3. Data for each descriptor variable for the training set:

All

6.4. Data for the dependent variable (response) for the training set:

All

6.5. Other information about the training set:

Dataset was split into training (T) and validation (V) sets by following the “1:Z algorithm”. Training set consist of 40 compounds.

6.6. Pre-processing of data before modelling:

Standard scaler - Standardize features by removing the mean and scaling to unit variance.

6.7. Statistics for goodness-of-fit:

$R^2 = 0.923$

$RMSE_C = 0.855$

$MAE_C = 0.634$

6.8. Robustness – Statistics obtained by leave-one-out cross validation:

$Q2_{LOO} = 0.904$

$RMSE_{CV} = 0.953$

$MAE_{CV} = 0.707$

6.9. Robustness – Statistics obtained by leave-many-out cross validation:

N/A

6.10. Robustness – Statistics obtained by Y-scrambling:

$R^2_{SCR} = 0.075$

6.11. Robustness – Statistics obtained by bootstrap:

N/A

6.12. Robustness – Statistics obtained by other methods:

N/A

7. Defining predictivity – OECD Principle 4

7.1. Availability of the external validation set:

Yes

7.2. Availability information for the external validation set:

CAS RN:Yes
 Chemical Name:Yes
 Smiles:Yes
 Formula:No
 INChI:No
 MOL file:No

7.3. Data for each descriptor variable for the external validation set:

Yes

7.4. Data for the dependent variable (response) for the external validation set:

Yes

7.5. Other information about the external validation set:

Validation set consist of 19 compounds.

7.6. Experimental design of test set:

Every 3th compound in a group of chemicals, sorted by experimental values in ascending order, was assigned to the validation set.

7.7. Predictivity – Statistics obtained by external validation:

$$Q^2_{F1} = 0.906$$

$$Q^2_{F2} = 0.906$$

$$Q^2_{F3} = 0.921$$

$$RMSE_{EXT} = 0.864$$

$$MAE_{EXT} = 0.637$$

$$CCC_{EXT} = 0.948$$

7.8. Predictivity – Assessment of the external validation set:

Range of response for prediction set (n=19) compounds:

VP (mmHg): -4.81/3.87(range of corresponding training set: -6.08/5.98)

Range of modeling descriptors for prediction set (n=19) compounds:

F03[C-F]: 0/43 (range of corresponding training set: 0/41)

nDB: 0/2 (range of corresponding training set: 0/4)

AAC: 0.92/1.91(range of corresponding training set: 0.72/2.18)

7.9. Comments on the external validation of the model:

N/A

8. Providing a mechanistic interpretation – OECD Principle 5

8.1. Mechanistic basis of the model:

The model was developed by statistical approach. No mechanistic was defined a priori.

8.2. A priori or a posteriori mechanistic interpretation:

The original model published in Bhatarai B. and Gramatica P. [2]:

$$\log VP = 7.97 (\pm 1.26) - 0.16 (\pm 0.02) \times F03[C-F] - 3.16 (\pm 0.92) \times AAC - 0.64 (\pm 0.40) \times nDB$$

New model with extended applicability domain (AD) using calculated value of VP:

$$\log VP = -0.8314 (\pm 0.143) - 2.2117 (\pm 0.149) \times F03[C-F] - 0.2274 (\pm 0.180) \times nDB - 1.8076 (\pm 0.175) \times AAC$$

F03[C-F] - Frequency of C – F at topological distance 3

AAC - Mean information index on atomic composition

nDB - Number of double bonds

The vapor pressure of compounds belonging to the PFAS group decreases with all descriptors (F03[C-F], nDB, AAC).

8.3. Other information about the mechanistic interpretation:

N/A

9. Miscellaneous information

9.1. Comments:

Scopes of expansion of the field:

The expansion of the AD increased the range of descriptors in the space. in the case of VP, the maximum range of F03[C-F] increased from 39 to 43. The AAC descriptor was expanded from a value of 0.85 to 0.72 at the minimum and from 2.06 to 2.18 at the maximum. The values of the nDB descriptor did not change because it was in the space range of the other two descriptors.

9.2. Bibliography:

1. Sosnowska A., Mudlaff M., Gorb L., Bulawska N., Zdybel Sz., Bakker M., Peijnenburg W., Puzyn T.; *Extending the applicability domain of QSPRs for predicting water solubility and vapor pressure of PFAS, Chemosphere 2023, 340, 139965*
2. Bhatarai, B. & Gramatica, P. Prediction of Aqueous Solubility, Vapor Pressure and Critical Micelle Concentration for Aquatic Partitioning of Perfluorinated Chemicals. *Environ Sci Technol* 45, 8120–8128 (2011).

9.3. Supporting information:

10. Summary for the JRC QSAR Model Database (compiled by JRC)

10.1. QMRF number:

10.2. Publication date:

10.3. Keywords:

10.4. Comments:

2.1.3 QMRF for a predictive model for n-octanol/water coefficient (logK_{OW})

1. QSAR identifier

1.1. QSAR identifier (title):

QSPR model for predicting n-octanol/water coefficient (logK_{OW}) of PFAS compounds

1.2. Other related models:

N/A

1.3. Software coding the model:

Python 3.9.7.

2. General information

2.1. Date of QMRF:

May 2023

2.2. QMRF author(s) and contact details:

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80-172 Gdansk, Poland

+48 795 160 760

contact@qsarlab.com <https://www.qsarlab.com>

2.3. Date of QMRF update(s):

N/A

2.4. QMRF update(s):

N/A

2.5. Model developer(s) and contact details:

1. M. Mudlaff, QSAR Lab Ltd, m.mudlaff@qsarlab.com

2. N. Buławska, QSAR Lab Ltd, n.bulawska@qsarlab.com

2.6. Date of model development and/or publication:

Published in 2023

2.7. Reference(s) to main scientific papers and/or software package:

Mudlaff, M., Sosnowska, A., Grob, L., Bulawska, N., Jagiello, K., & Puzyn, T. (2024). Environmental impact of PFAS: Filling data gaps using theoretical quantum chemistry and QSPR modeling. *Environment International*, 185, (2024), 108568. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382313>

AlvaDesc: Mauri, A. (2020). alvaDesc: A tool to calculate and analyze molecular descriptors and fingerprints. In *Ecotoxicological QSARs* (pp. 801-820). Humana, New York, NY.

Python: Van Rossum, G., & Drake, F. L. (2009). *Python 3 Reference Manual*. Scotts Valley, CA: CreateSpace.

COSMO-RS: AMS 2022.1 COSMO-RS, SCM, Theoretical Chemistry, Vrije Universiteit, Amsterdam, The Netherlands. (2022).

2.8. Availability of information about the model:

The set of 89 PFAS compounds were selected to model development. Model was obtained based on two theoretical molecular descriptors (T(F..F) and gmin). Structures, names, acronyms, CAS numbers, and SMILES of PFAS examined in this study are listed in a Supplementary Information 1. For the modeling, the multiple linear regression (MLR) approach was applied.

2.9. Availability of another QMRF for exactly the same model:

N/A

3. Defining the endpoint – OECD Principle 1

3.1. Species:

N/A

3.2. Endpoint:

N-octanol/water coefficient (logK_{OW})

3.3. Comment on the endpoint:

N-octanol/water coefficient (logK_{OW}) of PFAS compounds

3.4. Endpoint units:

N/A

3.5. Dependent variable:

N-octanol/water coefficient ($\log K_{ow}$)

3.6. Experimental protocol:

Predictions were obtained according to Gaussian16 program. The impact of water mass has been considered as part of the COSMO approach. Solubility and vapor pressure were calculated using the COSMO-RS technique, which is included in the ADM software package. To obtain the physical properties, COSMO-RS treats polarization charge densities calculated in the COSMO-RS option of Gaussian16.

3.7. Endpoint data quality and variability:

Data were simulated for 88 compounds, where 6 compounds were rejected due to limitations of the program's computational capabilities. Calculated values were compared with experimental values based on their trend.

4. Defining the algorithm – OECD Principle 2

4.1. Type of model:

QSAR model -Multiple linear regression (MLR)

4.2. Explicit algorithm:

$$\log K_{ow} = 6.341 (\pm 0.097) + 1.639 (\pm 0.122) \times T(F..F) - 1.854 (\pm 0.122) \times gmin$$

4.3. Descriptors in the model:

1. sum of topological distances between F..F (T(F..F))
2. minimum atom E-state value in a molecule (gmin)

4.4. Descriptor selection:

Descriptors of the model available in the literature were used. Structural and 2D atom pairs descriptors, which have an influence on the solubility were selected. Pairs of descriptors between which correlation did not exceed 0.6 were selected.

4.5. Algorithm and descriptor generation:

Descriptors of the model available in the literature were used. Where the compounds were drawn using Hyperchem software and their energy was minimized using the AM1 semiempirical method. Descriptors in the original literature model were calculated in dragon software. The obtained 0D-3D descriptors were selected using a genetic algorithm.

In this publication, the descriptors were calculated using SMILES notation in alvaDesc software. They belong to constitutional indices, topological indices, walk and path counts, and molecular properties. The number of descriptors has been first reduced by constant values and by descriptors with no data for at least one compound.

4.6. Software name and version for descriptor generation:

alvaDesc software

4.7. Chemicals/ Descriptors ratio:

82 chemicals / 2 descriptors

5. Defining the applicability domain – OECD Principle 3

5.1. Description of the applicability domain of the model:

Applicability domain was verified based on a plot of the standardized residuals versus the leverage values, so-called Williams plot. All compounds used in the training and validation sets should be situated in the range of residuals differing by ± 3 standard deviations from the mean value. They should not also exceed the h^* value.

5.2. Method used to assess the applicability domain:

As it has been noted in section 5.1, the applicability domain of the model was assessed by the leverage approach, providing a cut-off hat value ($h^*=0.145$). The response applicability domain was also verified by the standardized residuals.

5.3. Software name and version for applicability domain assessment:

Williams plot was generated in Python 3.9.7.

5.4. Limits of applicability:

Two compounds (8:2 Fluorotelomer phosphate diester and perfluorooctadecanoic acid) was classified as outlier, because its leverage value was higher than h^* .

6. Defining goodness-of-fit and robustness – OECD Principle 4
6.1. Availability of the training set:

Yes

6.2. Availability information for the training set:

CAS RN: Yes

Chemical Name: Yes

Smiles: Yes

Formula: No

INChI: No

MOL file: No

6.3. Data for each descriptor variable for the training set:

All

6.4. Data for the dependent variable (response) for the training set:

All

6.5. Other information about the training set:

Dataset was split into training (T) and validation (V) sets by following the “1:Z algorithm”. Training set consist of 55 compounds.

6.6. Pre-processing of data before modelling:

Standard scaler - Standardize features by removing the mean and scaling to unit variance.

6.7. Statistics for goodness-of-fit:

$R^2 = 0.946$

$RMSE_C = 0.748$

$MAE_C = 0.597$

6.8. Robustness – Statistics obtained by leave-one-out cross validation:

$Q2_{LOO} = 0.934$

$RMSE_{CV} = 0.825$

$MAE_{CV} = 0.644$

6.9. Robustness – Statistics obtained by leave-many-out cross validation:

N/A

6.10. Robustness – Statistics obtained by Y-scrambling:

$R^2_{SCR} = 0.030$

6.11. Robustness – Statistics obtained by bootstrap:

N/A

6.12. Robustness – Statistics obtained by other methods:

N/A

7. Defining predictivity – OECD Principle 4
7.1. Availability of the external validation set:

Yes

7.2. Availability information for the external validation set:

CAS RN:Yes

Chemical Name:Yes

Smiles:Yes

Formula:No

INChI:No

MOL file:No

7.3. Data for each descriptor variable for the external validation set:

Yes

7.4. Data for the dependent variable (response) for the external validation set:

Yes

7.5. Other information about the external validation set:

Validation set consist of 27 compounds.

7.6. Experimental design of test set:

Every 3th compound in a group of chemicals, sorted by experimental values in ascending order, was assigned to the validation set.

7.7. Predictivity – Statistics obtained by external validation:

$Q^2_{F1} = 0.916$

$Q^2_{F2} = 0.916$

$Q^2_{F3} = 0.927$

$RMSE_{EXT} = 0.870$

$MAE_{EXT} = 0.704$

$CCC_{EXT} = 0.957$

7.8. Predictivity – Assessment of the external validation set:

Range of response for prediction set (n=27)

compounds:

LogK_{OW} : 2.08/12.82 (range of correspondig training set: 0.72/16.17)

Range of modeling descriptors for prediction set (n=27)

compounds:

T(F..F): 6/3380 (range of corresponding training set: 6/6360)

gmin: -10.14/-4.30 (range of corresponding training set: -10.38/-2.91)

7.9. Comments on the external validation of the model:

N/A

8. Providing a mechanistic interpretation – OECD Principle 5

8.1. Mechanistic basis of the model:

The model was developed by statistical approach. No mechanistic was defined a priori.

8.2. A priori or a posteriori mechanistic interpretation:

N/A

8.3. Other information about the mechanistic interpretation:

N/A

9. Miscellaneous information

9.1. Comments:

9.2. Bibliography:

Mudlaff, M., Sosnowska, A., Grob, L., Bulawska, N., Jagiello, K., & Puzyn, T. (2024). Environmental impact of PFAS: Filling data gaps using theoretical quantum chemistry and QSPR modeling. Environment International, 185, (2024), 108568. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11382313>

9.3. Supporting information:

N/A

10. Summary for the JRC QSAR Model Database (compiled by JRC)

10.1. QMRF number:

10.2. Publication date:

10.3. Keywords:

2.1.4 QMRF for a predictive model for bioconcentration factor (BCF)

1. QSAR identifier

1.1. QSAR identifier (title):

QSPR model for predicting PFAS bioconcentration factor

1.2. Other related models:

N/A

1.3. Software coding the model:

Python 3.8.8

2. General information

2.1. Date of QMRF:

May 2023

2.2. QMRF author(s) and contact details:

QSAR Lab Sp. z o.o.

Trzy Lipy 3 Street, Building B,

80-172 Gdansk, Poland

+48 795 160 760

contact@qsarlab.com <https://www.qsarlab.com>

2.3. Date of QMRF update(s):

N/A

2.4. QMRF update(s):

N/A

2.5. Model developer(s) and contact details:

D. Kowalska, QSAR Lab Ltd, d.kowalska@qsarlab.com

A. Sosnowska, QSAR Lab Ltd, a.sosnowska@qsarlab.com

2.6. Date of model development and/or publication:

Published in 2023

2.7. Reference(s) to main scientific papers and/or software package:

1. alvaDesc

Mauri, A. (2020). alvaDesc: A Tool to Calculate and Analyze Molecular Descriptors and Fingerprints. In K. Roy (Ed.), Ecotoxicological QSARs (pp. 801–820). Humana Press Inc. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-0716-0150-1_32

2. Python 3.8.8

Python Software Foundation. Python Language Reference, version 3.8.8. Available at <http://www.python.org>

2.8. Availability of information about the model:

By using experimental data for bioconcentration factors (BCF) for 33 PFAS, multiple linear regression (MLR) model was developed using molecular descriptors selected from a large set of 1D-3D calculated descriptors by genetic algorithm (GA). Model utilizes four molecular descriptors: GATS2v, P_VSA_e_5, E3m, nCp.

2.9. Availability of another QMRF for exactly the same model:

N/A

3. Defining the endpoint – OECD Principle 1

3.1. Species:

N/A

3.2. Endpoint:

Log BCF

3.3. Comment on the endpoint:

Bioconcentration factor

3.4. Endpoint units:

L/kg

3.5. Dependent variable:

Log BCF

3.6. Experimental protocol:

Experimental data was considered from literature (Burkard et al., 2021). Bioconcentration factors are measured in the laboratory using standardized protocols with aquatic organisms and a water-borne exposure procedure (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development 2012; US Environmental Protection Agency 2016). Tests are typically run with a 28-d uptake phase followed by a depuration phase running from 14 to 28 d depending on the chemical (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development 2012; US Environmental Protection Agency 2016).

3.7. Endpoint data quality and variability:

To develop a QSPR model that predict BCF for PFAS, we used an available experimental data from previously published review study by Burkard. The dataset consisted of 33 compounds encompassing perfluorinated carboxylic acids (PFCAs), perfluorinated sulfonic acids (PFSA), fluorotelomer alcohols (FTOHs), and other related PFAS. Experimentally determined BCFs were obtained in laboratory conditions for Teleostei taxonomic class (whole body).

4. Defining the algorithm – OECD Principle 2

4.1. Type of model:

QSPR model – Multiple linear regression (MLR)

4.2. Explicit algorithm:

$$\log \text{BCF} = 3.01 + 1.78 \cdot \text{GATS2v} - 0.7 \cdot \text{P_VSA_e_5} - 0.8 \cdot \text{E3m} + 1.27 \cdot \text{nCp}$$

4.3. Descriptors in the model:

1. GATS2v—Geary autocorrelation of lag 2 weighted by van der Waals volume (2D – Autocorrelation)
2. P_VSA_e_5—P_VSA-like on Sanderson electronegativity, bin 5 (2D – P_VSA_like descriptor)
3. E3m—3rd component accessibility directional WHIM index / weighted by mass (3D – WHIM)
4. nCp—number of terminal primary C(sp³) (2D – Functional group counts)

4.4. Descriptor selection:

To select the optimal combination of calculated descriptors genetic algorithm (GA) was used.

4.5. Algorithm and descriptor generation:

The geometries of PFAS were optimized using the quantum mechanical method (PM7) implemented in MOPAC 2016 software, and a total of 1869 1D-3D descriptors of different types were calculated using alvaDesc software. They belong to constitutional indices, topological indices, walk and path counts, WHIM, and molecular properties.

4.6. Software name and version for descriptor generation:

1. alvaDesc software

Mauri, A. (2020). alvaDesc: A Tool to Calculate and Analyze Molecular Descriptors and Fingerprints. In K. Roy (Ed.), Ecotoxicological QSARs (pp. 801–820). Humana Press Inc.

<https://www.alvascience.com/alvadesc/>

2. MOPAC 2016 software

Stewart Computational Chemistry. Stewart J.J.P., Colorado Springs, CO, USA

<http://openmopac.net>

4.7. Chemicals/ Descriptors ratio:

22 chemicals in the training set / 4 descriptors

5. Defining the applicability domain – OECD Principle 3

5.1. Description of the applicability domain of the model:

Applicability domain was verified based on a plot of the standardized residuals versus the leverage values, so-called Williams plot. All compounds used in the training and validation sets should be situated in the range of residuals differing by ± 3 standard deviations from the mean value. They should not also exceed the h^* value.

5.2. Method used to assess the applicability domain:

As it has been noted in section 5.1, the applicability domain of the model was assessed by the leverage approach, providing a cut-off hat value ($h^*=0.682$). The response applicability domain was also verified by the standardized residuals.

5.3. Software name and version for applicability domain assessment:

Williams plot was generated in Python 3.8.8.

5.4. Limits of applicability:

One compounds (SamPAP) was classified as outlier, because its leverage value was higher than h^* .

6. Defining goodness-of-fit and robustness – OECD Principle 4

6.1. Availability of the training set:

Yes

6.2. Availability information for the training set:

CAS RN:Yes

Chemical Name:Yes

Smiles:Yes

Formula:No

INChI:No

MOL file:No

6.3. Data for each descriptor variable for the training set:

All

6.4. Data for the dependent variable (response) for the training set:

All

6.5. Other information about the training set:

Dataset was split into training (T) and validation (V) sets by following the “1:Z algorithm”.

Training set consist of 22 compounds.

6.6. Pre-processing of data before modelling:

Before the data were used for statistical analyses, a logarithm transformation was performed.

6.7. Statistics for goodness-of-fit:

$R^2 = 0.924$

$RMSE_C = 0.58$

$MAE_C = 0.49$

6.8. Robustness – Statistics obtained by leave-one-out cross validation:

$Q^2_{LOO} = 0.882$

$RMSE_{CV} = 0.73$

$MAE_{CV} = 0.63$

6.9. Robustness – Statistics obtained by leave-many-out cross validation:

N/A

6.10. Robustness – Statistics obtained by Y-scrambling:

$R^2_{Y_{SCR}} = 0.19$

6.11. Robustness – Statistics obtained by bootstrap:

N/A

6.12. Robustness – Statistics obtained by other methods:

N/A

7. Defining predictivity – OECD Principle 4

7.1. Availability of the external validation set:

Yes

7.2. Availability information for the external validation set:

CAS RN:Yes

Chemical Name:Yes

Smiles:Yes

Formula:No

INChI:No

MOL file:No

7.3. Data for each descriptor variable for the external validation set:

Yes

7.4. Data for the dependent variable (response) for the external validation set:

Yes

7.5. Other information about the external validation set:

Validation set consist of 11 compounds.

7.6. Experimental design of test set:

Every 3th compound in a group of chemicals, sorted by experimental values in ascending order, was assigned to the validation set.

7.7. Predictivity – Statistics obtained by external validation:

$Q^2_{F1} = 0.890$

$Q^2_{F2} = 0.888$

$Q^2_{F3} = 0.883$

$RMSE_{EXT} = 0.72$

$MAE_{EXT} = 0.57$

$CCC_{EXT} = 0.94$

7.8. Predictivity – Assessment of the external validation set:

Range of response for prediction set (n=11)

compounds:

log BCF): 0.98/8.30 (range of corresponding training set: -0.05/8.52)

Range of modeling descriptors for prediction set (n=11)

compounds:

nCp: 1/3 (range of corresponding training set: 1/4)

P_VSA_e_5: 44.05/94.53 (range of corresponding training set: 29.36/159.86)

E3m: 0.40/0.64 (range of corresponding training set: 0.34/0.64)

GATS2v: 1.1.8/1.4 (range of corresponding training set: 0.91/1.40)

7.9. Comments on the external validation of the model:

N/A

8. Providing a mechanistic interpretation – OECD Principle 5

8.1. Mechanistic basis of the model:

The model was developed by statistical approach. No mechanistic was defined a priori.

8.2. A priori or a posteriori mechanistic interpretation:

The PFAS bioconcentration in fish depends on dimensional features (descriptors), and on molecular properties (e.g bonds length, atom distribution, functional groups).

8.3. Other information about the mechanistic interpretation:

N/A

9. Miscellaneous information

9.1. Comments:

N/A

9.2. Bibliography:

Kowalska, D., Sosnowska, A. & Puzyn, T. Structure-property modeling of bioconcentration factor (BCF) for Per- and Polyfluoroalkyl Substances (PFAS). *Under revision step in Chemosphere (2024)*

9.3. Supporting information:

N/A

2.1.5 QMRF for a predictive model for melting point (MP)

1. QSAR identifier

1.1. QSAR identifier (title):

CADASTER QSPR Models for Predictions of Melting Point of Perfluorinated Chemicals

1.2. Other related models:

N/A

1.3. Software coding the model:

N/A

2. General information

2.1. Date of QMRF:

6/12/2021

2.2. QMRF author(s) and contact details:

QSAR Lab Ltd. Trzy Lipy 3 Street. Building B, 80-172 Gdansk +48 795160760

contact@qsarlab.com <https://www.qsarlab.com/en/>

2.3. Date of QMRF update(s):

N/A

2.4. QMRF update(s):

N/A

2.5. Model developer(s) and contact details:

Paola Gramatica Insubria University Department of Theoretical and Applied Sciences (DiSTA), via J.H.

Dunant 3, 21100 Varese (Italy) +390332421573 paola.gramatica@uninsubria.it <http://www.qsar.it/>

2.6. Date of model development and/or publication:

Published in 2011

2.7. Reference(s) to main scientific papers and/or software package:

[1]Bhatarai, B., Teetz, W., Liu, T., Öberg, T., Jeliaskova, N., Kochev, N., Pukalov, O., Tetko, I.V., Kovarich, S., Papa, E., Gramatica, P. (2011). CADASTER QSPR Models for Predictions of Melting and Boiling Points of Perfluorinated Chemicals. *Molecular Informatics*, 30(2-3), 189–204.

<https://doi.org/10.1002/minf.201000133>

[2]DRAGON

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/216208341_DRAGON_software_An_easy_approach_to_molecular_descriptor_calculations

2.8. Availability of information about the model:

For MP, 94 compounds (93 for HMGU) containing mainly long chain alkylates, saturated cyclic and few aromatic PFCs were split into training and prediction set close to 50% and 15 more compounds from PERFORCE were used as EV- set. More information about model attached in supplementary materials:

doi:10.1002/minf.201000133

2.9. Availability of another QMRF for exactly the same model:

N/A

3. Defining the endpoint – OECD Principle 1

3.1. Species:

N/A

3.2. Endpoint:

Melting Point

3.3. Comment on the endpoint:

Melting Point (MP) is an important endpoint as it influence the transport, solubility, distribution and environmental fate.

3.4. Endpoint units:

°C

3.5. Dependent variable:

MP

3.6. Experimental protocol:

N/A

3.7. Endpoint data quality and variability:

- 55 data points of physiochemical property were collected mainly from SRC-PhysProp
- 19 data points from Trepka et al. [2]
- 7 data points from Gajewski et al. [3]
- 13 data points from Platonov et al. [4]

4. Defining the algorithm – OECD Principle 2

4.1. Type of model:

UI: Multiple linear regression model (OLS - Ordinary Least Square)

LNU: Partial least squares regression (PLSR)

IDEA: Multiple linear regression model (OLS - Ordinary Least Square)

HMGU: Associative neural networks (ASNN)

4.2. Explicit algorithm:

UI/HMGU: $MP = -209.04 (\pm 139.9) + 132.95 (\pm 22.63) \times ACC + 3.04 (\pm 0.97) \times F02[C-F] - 18.97 (\pm 7.98) \times C-013 + 209.04 (\pm 139.9) \times RBF$

LNU: $IDEA: MP = 2.34(\pm 0.28) \ln 2W - 164.76(\pm 16.51) WrelF \pm 33.14(\pm 8.90) NHBDON + 79.38$

4.3. Descriptors in the model:

[1]ACC - 'information indices' which characterizes mean information index on atomic composition

[2]F02[C-F] - frequency of C-F at topological distance 2

[3]C-013 - carbon connected to at least three electronegative atoms (X) CRX3

[4]RBF - rotatable bond fraction

[5]ln2W - general degree of branching through the square of the logarithm of Wiener index

[6]WrelF - the number of fluorine atoms and their relative connectivity (this is the sum of all paths to fluorine atoms divided by the Wiener index W)

[7]NHBDON - denotes the number of H-bond donors in the molecule

4.4. Descriptor selection:

UI: - highly correlated descriptors were excluded (more than 90% pairwise correlation)

- filtered descriptors were subject to variable selection method using genetic algorithm (GA)

- using selected descriptors a multiple linear regression (MLR) model by using the ordinary-least-squares (OLS) techniques were built

LNU:

- PLSR was used for data analysis and modeling

- the data analysis and multivariate calibrations were carried out with the software SIMCA-P

IDEA:

- descriptors were chosen manually in a step-wise manner based on expert knowledge

- choice of descriptors combination was guided by three practical rules: (1) each coefficient in the MLRA must be statistically significant based on RSD (RSD < 25%); (2) the choice of extra descriptors obeys a chemical logic in order to fix compounds with bad model values trying to handle the missing structural fragments; (3) successively selected descriptors must decrease

RMSE value and increase Q² and R² values

HMGU: OCHEM database

4.5. Algorithm and descriptor generation:

UI, LNU: The input files for descriptor calculation were obtained by the semi empirical AM1 method (minimized their lowest energy conformation) using HYPERCHEM software. Molecular descriptors were generated using DRAGON software.

IDEA: set of topological, constitutional and group based descriptors were calculated using JBSMM software

HMGU: For each atom type in a molecule the E-state indices are summed and are used in a group contribution manner. Constant values and descriptors that had Pearson pairwise correlation greater than 95% were excluded and all remaining indices were used to build models.

4.6. Software name and version for descriptor generation:

DRAGON software

A software to calculate theoretical molecular descriptors

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/216208341_DRAGON_software_An_easy_approach_to_molecular_descriptor_calculations

HYPERCHEM

Software used for molecular drawing and conformational energy optimization AM1

www.hyper.com

JBSMM software

N. Kochev, O. Pukalov, Software system for molecular modeling—JBSMM; Scientific Researches of the Union of Scientists in Bulgaria – Plovdiv, Series C: Technics and Technologies, Vol. V., Balkan Conference of Young Scientists; Plovdiv, 16–18 June, 2005, pp. 315 – 320.

SIMCA-P

SIMCA-P, v.11.0 Umetrics AB, Umea, Sweden

<http://www.umetrics.com/simca>

OCHEM (on-line CHEMICAL database and Modeling environment)

<https://www.ochem.eu/home/show.do>

4.7. Chemicals/ Descriptors ratio:

N/A

5. Defining the applicability domain – OECD Principle 3

5.1. Description of the applicability domain of the model:

UI, IDEA: The Williams plot was used to verify the presence of response outliers (i.e. compounds with cross-validated standardized residuals greater than three standard deviation units, ± 3) and chemicals very influential for their structure in determining model parameters (i.e. compounds with high leverage value (h) ($h > h^*$, the critical value being $h^* = 3p'/n$, where p' is the number of model variables plus one, and n the number of the objects used to calculate the model). The hat (high leverage h) value is different for each model. The leverage approach was applied for the definition of the structural chemical domain of each model for new chemicals without experimental data.

LNU: Residual standard deviation (the Euclidean distance to the PLSR model) and the leverage (the Mahalanobis distance within the PLSR model space).

HMGU: The distance to model based on standard deviation of ensemble prediction was used. The DM was calibrated using 5-fold cross-validation values (i.e., for each DM value the corresponding prediction error was estimated). Using this calibrated DM the accuracy of prediction for any new molecule can be estimated. The standard deviations, which covered 95% of compounds from the training set, were used as ADs of the HMGU models. These ADs were used to compare results with other approaches reported in this study

5.2. Method used to assess the applicability domain:

UI, IDEA: leverage (williams) and standardization approach

LNU: Residual standard deviation (the Euclidean distance to the PLSR model) and the leverage (the Mahalanobis distance within the PLSR model space) approach

HMGU: The AD of models was estimated using standard deviation (STD) of ensembles of neural network models.

5.3. Software name and version for applicability domain assessment:

N/A

5.4. Limits of applicability:

UI: The leverage approach based AD study has a hat cut-off values for the MP MLR model of 0.16. Based on this cut-off, there were four training compounds (CAS 306-91-2, CAS 311-89-7, CAS 338-83-0 and CAS 359-70-6) which were outside the structural applicability domain of MP model that why they were highly influential in selecting modeling variables. In addition there were 16 other new compounds which were out of the structural domain (high leverage or high hat values). They were bulky polyfluorinated chemicals, mostly linear PFCs with 13 or 15 carbon atom long including 2 acrylates and nitrogen centered

PFCs. These long chain PFCs were probably extrapolated as the longest compound in the training model were with 7 carbon atoms only. Altogether only 20/397 compounds are found to be out of AD, thus the model has 94.9 % coverage.

IDEA: Applicability domain for melting point shows that there are only five compounds out of 303 compounds that are not satisfying the criteria used leverage value smaller than the warning leverage value ($h^*=0.16$)

LNU: 94 compounds were used with MP as a calibration set to study applicability domain, 37 descriptors with the highest values selected using VIP were used to domain study. 20 compounds with a probability of belonging of less than 1 % ($P_{ModXPS} < 0.01$) were considered to be outliers, in which P_{ModXPS} represents the probability of the observation belonging to the model in the X space. After excluding outliers in the calibration model, 83.69 % variance in Y is described, and 83.2 % variance is predicted by the model at 1 component. Then 303 compounds without any MP values were used further to determine their domain, the distance to the model may be augmented with $P_{ModXPS+}$ measuring how far outside the acceptable model domain the projection of the observation falls. 145 compounds were found to be outside the domain using $P_{ModXPS+}$ approach that combines P_{ModXPS} plus Hotelling's T2. The strong outliers were determined by Hotelling's T2 diagnosis at 99 % confidence interval.

HMGU: The AD of models was estimated using standard deviation (STD) of ensembles of neural network models. As aforementioned, the STD covering 95% of molecules within the training set as the AD of the model was selected. For melting point, this cutoff STD value is 418, corresponding to a predicted RMSE of 50°C. Out of 303 new compounds, 212 were inside of AD of the model, i.e. we expect that their average predicted errors are below 50°. The remaining 91 compounds were outside of AD and thus we expect that their average errors are above 50 K. Several compounds had extremely large STD values > 100°. These compounds are all cyclic carbonic acid esters of 2- (hydroxymethyl)-1,3-propanediol. They all have bridged ring structures with three ether bonds. The estimation of contributions of these structural features for MP is difficult since there are no similar structures in the training set.

6. Defining goodness-of-fit and robustness – OECD Principle 4

6.1. Availability of the training set:

Yes

6.2. Availability information for the training set:

CAS RN: No

Chemical Name: Yes

Smiles: Yes

Formula: Yes

INChI: No

MOL file: No

6.3. Data for each descriptor variable for the training set:

All

6.4. Data for the dependent variable (response) for the training set:

All

6.5. Other information about the training set:

94 compounds were split into training and prediction set using to methods: by SOM and Random on the data. The two trainings sets - of 53 chemicals (SOM) and 48 chemicals (Random) were used to develop a population of models.

HMGU: same data excluding compound #102, CAS 1691-99-2

6.6. Pre-processing of data before modelling:

All descriptor variables were preprocessed by auto-scaling to zero mean and unit variance.

6.7. Statistics for goodness-of-fit:

a) split by SOM

UI: R^2 :0.83; $RMSE_{TR}$: 33.95;

LNU: R^2 : 0.89; $RMSE_{TR}$: 28.17;

IDEA: R^2 : 0.86; $RMSE_{TR}$ 31.03;

HMGU: R^2 : 0.80; $RMSE_{TR}$: 39.00

b) response splitting

UI: R^2 : 0.84; $RMSE_{TR}$: 37.16;

LNU: R^2 : 0.89; $RMSE_{TR}$: 32.42;

IDEA: R^2 : 0.84; $RMSE_{TR}$: 37.15;

HMGU: R^2 : 0.81; $RMSE_{TR}$: 43.00

FULL MODEL:

UI: R^2 : 0.80; $RMSE_{TR}$: 40.24;

LNU: R^2 : 0.82; $RMSE_{TR}$: 38.64;

IDEA: R^2 : 0.79; $RMSE_{TR}$: 40.67;

HMGU: R^2 : 0.85; $RMSE_{TR}$: 37.00

Consensus: R^2 : 0.88; $RMSE_{TR}$: 31.81

6.8. Robustness – Statistics obtained by leave-one-out cross validation:

a) split by SOM

UI: Q_{LOO}^2 : 0.79;

LNU: Q_{LOO}^2 : 0.84;

b) response splitting

UI: Q_{LOO}^2 : 0.79;

LNU: Q_{LOO}^2 : 0.81;

FULL MODEL

UI: Q_{LOO}^2 : 0.78;

LNU: Q_{LOO}^2 : 0.82;

IDEA: Q_{LOO}^2 : 0.77;

6.9. Robustness – Statistics obtained by leave-many-out cross validation:

N/A

6.10. Robustness – Statistics obtained by Y-scrambling:

a) split by SOM

UI: R_Y^2 : 0.07

b) response splitting

UI: R_Y^2 : 0.08

FULL MODEL

UI: R_Y^2 : 0.04

IDEA: R_Y^2 : 0.03

6.11. Robustness – Statistics obtained by bootstrap:

a) split by SOM

UI: Q_{BOOT}^2 : 0.78

EV: Q_{BOOT}^2 : 0.77

b) response splitting

UI: Q_{BOOT}^2 : 0.78

EV: Q_{BOOT}^2 : 0.78

FULL MODEL UI: Q_{BOOT}^2 : 0.77

6.12. Robustness – Statistics obtained by other methods:

N/A

7. Defining predictivity – OECD Principle 4

7.1. Availability of the external validation set:

Yes

7.2. Availability information for the external validation set:

CAS RN:Yes

Chemical Name:Yes

Smiles:Yes

Formula:No

INChI:No

MOL file:No

7.3. Data for each descriptor variable for the external validation set:

All

7.4. Data for the dependent variable (response) for the external validation set:

All

7.5. Other information about the external validation set:

15 compounds for PERFORCE were used for external validation as EV-set.

7.6. Experimental design of test set:

EV-set contains long chain perfluoroalkylated chemicals which are prevalent in the environment and are of higher interest in terms of physico- chemical properties and environmental distribution.

7.7. Predictivity – Statistics obtained by external validation:

a) split by SOM

UI: $RMSE_{ext}$: 51.69; Q_{F1}^2 : 0.76; Q_{F3}^2 :0.62;

EV-set: $RMSE_{ext}$: 24.92; Q_{F1}^2 : 0.72; Q_{F3}^2 :0.91; EV-set: R_{YS}^2 :0.08

LNU: $RMSE_{ext}$: 42.05 EV-set: $RMSE_{ext}$: 16.4

IDEA: $RMSE_{ext}$: 21.71; Q_{F1}^2 : 0.76; Q_{F3}^2 :0.61

EV-set: $RMSE_{ext}$: 36.88; Q_{F1}^2 : 0.39; Q_{F3}^2 :0.80;

HMGU: $RMSE_{ext}$: 46.00 EV-set: $RMSE_{ext}$: 39.00

b) response splitting

UI: $RMSE_{ext}$: 45.47; Q_{F1}^2 : 0.73; Q_{F3}^2 :0.76;

EV-set: $RMSE_{ext}$: 32.08; Q_{F1}^2 : 0.73; Q_{F3}^2 :0.87; EV-set: R_{YS}^2 : 0.08

LNU: $RMSE_{ext}$: 37.82; Q_{F1}^2 : -; Q_{F3}^2 :-

EV-set: $RMSE_{ext}$: 30.67; Q_{F1}^2 : -; Q_{F3}^2 :-;

IDEA: $RMSE_{ext}$: 46.06; Q_{F1}^2 : 0.72; Q_{F3}^2 :0.76

EV-set: $RMSE_{ext}$: 42.02; Q_{F1}^2 : 0.56; Q_{F3}^2 :0.79;

HMGU: $RMSE_{ext}$: 47.00; Q_{F1}^2 : -; Q_{F3}^2 :-

EV-set: $RMSE_{ext}$: 40.00

FULL MODEL:

UI: $RMSE_{ext}$: 27.19; Q_{F1}^2 : 0.83; Q_{F3}^2 :0.91;

LNU: $RMSE_{ext}$: 25.96

IDEA: $RMSE_{ext}$: 38.82; Q_{F1}^2 :0.65; Q_{F3}^2 :0.81

HMGU: $RMSE_{ext}$: 34.00

7.8. Predictivity – Assessment of the external validation set:

N/A

7.9. Comments on the external validation of the model:

N/A

8. Providing a mechanistic interpretation – OECD Principle 5

8.1. Mechanistic basis of the model:

N/A

8.2. A priori or a posteriori mechanistic interpretation:

UI/HMGU: $MP = -209.04 (\pm 139.9) + 132.95 (\pm 22.63) \times ACC + 3.04 (\pm 0.97) \times F02[C-F] - 18.97 (\pm 7.98) \times C-013 + 209.04 (\pm 139.9) \times RBF$

where:

ACC - 'information indices' which characterizes mean information index on atomic composition

F02[C-F] - Frequency of C-F at topological distance 2

C-013 - carbon connected to at least three electronegative atoms (X) CRX3

RBF - rotatable bond fraction

LNU: IDEA: $MP = 2.34(\pm 0.28) \ln 2W - 164.76(\pm 16.51)WrelF \pm 33.14(\pm 8.90)NHBDon + 79.38$

where:

In2W - general degree of branching through the square of the logarithm of Wiener index

WrelF- the number of fluorine atoms and their relative connectivity (this is the sum of all paths to fluorine atoms divided by the Wiener index W)

NHBDON - denotes the number of H-bond donors in the molecule

8.3. Other information about the mechanistic interpretation:

N/A

9. Miscellaneous information

9.1. Comments:

9.2. Bibliography:

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[3] R. P. Gajewski, G. D. Thompson, E. H. Chio, J. *Agric. Food Chem.* 1988, 36, 174–177.

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9.3. Supporting information:

Training set(s) Test set(s)

10. Summary for the JRC QSAR Model Database (compiled by JRC)

10.1. QMRF number:

10.2. Publication date:

10.3. Keywords:

2.1.6 Predicted and calculated environmental endpoints for PFAS considered in PROMISCES

Improved, newly developed, and adopted *in silico* tools, as well as the appropriate mathematical transformations were then applied for estimating physicochemical properties (S_w , VP, $\log K_{ow}$ BCF, MP, K_H , $\log K_{AW}$, $\log K_{OA}$, and $\log K_{OC}$) for 71 PFAS defined within the PROMISCES project. The results of the predictions with the indications of whether the predictions are in the applicability domain of the models are presented in Table 4.

To assess the boundaries of the obtained models, two different approaches were employed depending on the availability of experimental data for the chemical compounds.

For compounds with available experimental data, an analysis was conducted leverage approach (Williams plot). Compounds falling within the boundaries defined by $0 < \text{leverage} < h^*$ and $|r| < 3$ (where h^* is the critical leverage value and r are standardized residuals) were considered reliable predictions and were marked as black in Table 4. Compounds outside these boundaries were considered less reliable: those exceeding the h^* value were marked in red, while those with residuals greater than 3 standard deviation units (but do not exceed critical leverage values) were marked in blue. Red markings indicated compounds for which the QSAR model might provide less accurate values, whereas blue markings suggested that the predictions could be correct but come with a larger margin of uncertainty. This color coding was consistently applied in Table 4.

In the absence of experimental data for a given compound, the applicability domain was evaluated on the basis of the leverage values. In particular, compounds were deemed to fall within the applicability domain of the model if their leverage values did not exceed the critical value h^* (which may vary depending on the specific model in question), and if the predicted values fell within the range covered by the training data set. The aforementioned compounds were indicated in black in Table 4. Conversely, compounds with leverage values exceeding h^* were indicated in red, suggesting that their predicted values may diverge significantly from the actual values. Additionally, compounds with predicted values that fell outside the range of the training data (but do not exceed the critical leverage value) were indicated in blue, indicating that the predictions were extrapolated and should be interpreted with caution.

Table 4: Estimated environmental endpoints for 71 PFAS defined for the analysis in the PROMISCES project

ID	Name	CAS	Sw [log mg/L]	VP [log mmHg]	k _H [mol · Pa ⁻¹ · m ⁻³]	LogK _{AW}	LogK _{OW}	LogK _{OA}	LogK _{OC}	MP [°C]	BCF
1	Acetic acid, 2,2-difluoro-2-[[2,2,4,5-tetrafluoro-5-(trifluoromethoxy)-1,3-dioxolan-4-yl]oxy]-, ammonium salt (1:1)	1190931-27-1	3.41	-3.42	139.92	-1.25	4.13	5.38	4.06	14.31	-0.83
2	10:2 Acid sulfonic fluorotelomer	120226-60-0	0.25	-6.35	47.61	-1.72	8.81	10.53	8.66	160.18	1.613
3	2-perfluoro-propoxypropanoic acid	13252-13-6	2.86	-2.41	4.21	-2.77	5.34	8.11	5.25	-4.57	1.78
4	7-H-Perfluoroheptanoic acid	1546-95-8	2.35	-3.43	13.32	-2.27	5.95	8.22	5.85	93.75	-0.13
5	N-methyl perfluorobutane sulfonamido acetic acid, n=4	159381-10-9	3.92	-3.90	1355.62	-0.26	5.30	5.56	5.21	100.28	-4.81
6	Perfluorooctadecanoic acid (PFODA)	16517-11-6	-6.52	-8.00	0.00	-7.01	15.11	22.11	14.85	187.64	3.48
7	Perfluoro-3,7-dimethyloctanoic acid	172155-07-6	0.74	-3.15	0.11	-4.34	8.34	12.68	8.20	19.65	4.12
8	perfluorotridecane sulfonic acid	174675-49-1	-2.56	-6.21	0.04	-4.76	11.16	15.92	10.97	134.27	-7.40
9	Perfluorooctane sulfonic acid	1763-23-1	0.92	-3.39	0.31	-3.91	7.68	11.59	7.55	79.46	3.36
10	hencosafluoroundecanoic acid	2058-94-8	-0.33	-4.65	0.28	-3.95	8.82	12.77	8.67	103.60	3.26
11	N-Methyl perfluorooctane sulfonamidoacetic acid	2355-31-9	1.97	-5.76	710.86	-0.54	7.73	8.27	7.60	136.58	-4.85
12	Perfluoropentanoic acid	2706-90-3	3.00	-1.20	0.46	-3.73	5.06	8.79	4.97	36.84	0.92
13	Perfluoropentane sulfonic acid	2706-91-4	2.49	-1.86	0.48	-3.71	5.93	9.64	5.83	50.39	0.67
14	6:2 Acid sulfonic fluorotelomer	27619-97-2	2.41	-4.37	105.39	-1.37	6.28	7.65	6.17	122.50	1.80
15	8:2 fluorotelomer carboxylic acid	27854-31-5	1.09	-3.68	0.93	-3.42	7.49	10.92	7.36	104.81	2.81
16	Perfluorooctane sulfonamidoacetic acid	2806-24-8	199	-5.54	448.89	-0.74	7.73	8.47	7.59	136.47	0.13
17	N-Ethyl perfluorooctane sulfonamidoacetic acid	2991-50-6	2.02	-5.86	978.78	-0.40	7.73	8.13	7.60	140.59	-1.42
18	Perfluoro-1-butanefulfonamide	30334-69-1	3.10	-3.01	32.05	-1.89	5.17	7.06	5.08	68.69	0.90
19	perfluorohexanoic acid	307-24-4	2.41	-1.01	0.06	-4.60	5.73	10.33	5.64	47.84	2.42
20	tricosafuorododecanoic acid	307-55-1	-0.98	-4.12	0.02	-5.16	9.53	14.69	9.36	115.24	2.68
21	N-Methyl perfluorooctane sulfonamide	31506-32-8	1.42	-4.85	27.14	-1.96	7.59	9.55	7.46	115.52	-2.69
22	pentadecafluorooctanoic acid*	335-67-1	1.34	-2.94	0.35	-3.85	6.96	10.81	6.84	69.67	1.67

Table 4 : Estimated environmental endpoints for 71 PFAS defined for the analysis in the PROMISCES project (cont.)

ID	Name	CAS	Sw [log mg/L]	VP [log mmHg]	k _H [mol · Pa ⁻¹ · m ⁻³]	LogK _{AW}	LogK _{OW}	LogK _{OA}	LogK _{OC}	MP [°C]	BCF
23	nonadecafluorodecanoic acid	335-76-2	0.26	-4.05	0.30	-3.92	8.18	12.10	8.04	92.11	2.31
24	Perfluorodecan sulfonic acid	335-77-3	-0.23	-4.43	0.20	-4.10	8.92	13.02	8.77	100.00	2.95
25	8:3 Fluorotelomer carboxylic acid	34598-33-9	1.33	-4.12	4.29	-2.76	7.46	10.22	7.33	117.93	2.04
26	Perfluorohexane sulfonic acid	355-46-4	1.96	-2.47	0.50	-3.69	6.51	10.20	6.40	59.93	1.78
27	3:3 fluorotelomer carboxylate	356-27-4	3.74	-1.26	3.09	-2.90	4.29	7.20	4.22	64.91	0.93
28	heptafluorobutanoic acid	375-22-4	3.68	-0.73	0.90	-3.44	4.37	7.81	4.30	25.07	1.21
29	Perfluorobutane sulfonic acid	375-73-5	3.05	-1.24	0.49	-3.71	5.28	8.98	5.19	40.60	0.64
30	tridecafluoroheptanoic acid	375-85-9	1.87	-1.84	0.10	-4.37	6.33	10.70	6.22	58.71	1.48
31	Perfluoroheptane sulfonic acid	375-92-8	1.44	-2.99	0.45	-3.74	7.10	10.84	6.98	69.58	4.33
32	heptadecafluorononanoic acid	375-95-1	0.82	-3.12	0.14	-4.25	7.54	11.79	7.41	80.80	2.85
33	Perfluorotetradecanoic acid (PFTeDA)	376-06-7	-2.47	-5.43	0.01	-5.41	11.08	16.49	10.89	138.95	2.90
34	8:2 Acid sulfonic fluorotelomer	39108-34-4	1.40	-5.32	74.64	-1.52	7.52	9.04	7.39	140.96	2.09
35	perfluorohexylphosphonic acid	40143-76-8	2.04	-2.78	1.24	-3.30	6.46	9.76	6.35	69.49	1.80
36	perfluorooctylphosphonic acid	40143-78-0	1.01	-3.67	0.72	-3.54	7.64	11.18	7.51	88.71	2.41
37	N-ethyl-1,1,2,2,3,3,4,4,5,5,6,6,7,7,8,8,8-heptadecafluorooctane-1-sulfonamide	4151-50-2	1.57	-6.65	2366.13	-0.02	7.59	7.61	7.46	123.92	1.53
38	perfluorohexanesulfonamide	41997-13-1	2.04	-3.56	7.61	-2.51	6.42	8.94	6.31	83.66	2.13
39	Perfluoropropane sulfonate	423-41-6	3.67	-1.54	4.92	-2.70	4.64	7.34	4.56	29.59	2.23
40	Perfluorohexane sulfonamidopropyl amine	50598-28-2	2.49	-4.36	108.80	-1.36	6.40	7.76	6.29	113.71	-1.93
41	perfluorodecylphosphonic acid	52299-26-0	-0.14	-4.68	0.43	-3.76	8.90	12.66	8.75	108.83	1.88
42	6:2 fluorotelomer carboxylic acid	53826-12-3	2.15	-2.69	1.37	-3.26	6.25	9.51	6.15	84.78	1.78
43	6:2 Fluorotelomerphosphatediester	57677-95-9	-2.96	-7.24	0.18	-4.13	10.84	14.97	10.65	174.41	2.52
44	Perfluoro-4-ethyl-hexanesulphonic acid	646-83-3	1.70	-4.99	80.32	-1.49	7.05	8.54	6.93	59.69	0.40
45	8:2 Fluorotelomerphosphatediester	678-41-1	-8.15	-9.62	0.00	-7.04	16.10	23.14	15.83	217.46	1.78
46	Perfluorohexadecanoic acid (PFHxDA)	67905-19-5	-4.30	-6.70	0.00	-6.03	12.91	18.94	12.69	163.11	3.17
47	Perfluorononan sulfonic acid	68259-12-1	0.36	-3.85	0.22	-4.05	8.29	12.33	8.14	89.60	3.04

Table 4 : Estimated environmental endpoints for 71 PFAS defined for the analysis in the PROMISCES project (cont.)

ID	Name	CAS	Sw [log mg/L]	VP [log mmHg]	k _H [mol · Pa ⁻¹ · m ⁻³]	LogK _{AW}	LogK _{OW}	LogK _{OA}	LogK _{OC}	MP [°C]	BCF
48	N-Methyl perfluorobutane sulfonamide	68298-12-4	3.49	-3.40	188.11	-1.12	5.13	6.25	5.04	83.38	-4.09
49	3,4,4,5,5,6,6,7,7,8,8,9,9,10,10,10-hexadecafluorodec-2-enoic acid	70887-84-2	2.01	-3.34	3.60	-2.84	7.19	10.02	7.06	87.80	1.38
50	Perfluorotridecanoic acid	72629-94-8	-1.69	-5.12	0.03	-4.90	10.26	15.17	10.09	127.03	3.37
51	Potassium 9-chlorohexadecafluoro-3-oxanonane-1-sulfonate	73606-19-6	1.51	-3.69	2.08	-3.08	7.22	10.30	7.10	58.65	-11.56
52	Perfluoroundecane sulfonic acid	749786-16-1	-0.88	-5.12	0.20	-4.09	9.61	13.69	9.44	110.66	3.10
53	Perfluorooctane sulfonamide	754-91-6	1.01	-4.35	3.43	-2.86	7.62	10.48	7.49	100.14	3.28
54	4:2 Acid sulfonic fluorotelomer	757124-72-4	3.38	-3.49	170.06	-1.16	4.96	6.12	4.87	103.77	3.04
55	Perfluorododecane sulfonic acid	79780-39-5	-1.59	-5.63	0.12	-4.33	10.34	14.67	10.17	121.53	2.55
56	7:3 fluorotelomer carboxylate	812-70-4	1.85	-3.59	4.67	-2.72	6.83	9.56	6.72	107.69	1.55
57	8:2 chlorinated perfluoroalkylether sulfonate	83329-89-9	0.36	-4.63	1.09	-3.36	8.56	11.92	8.42	75.21	-12.78
58	5:3 fluorotelomer carboxylate	914637-49-3	2.85	-2.58	5.91	-2.62	5.53	8.15	5.43	87.29	2.53
59	Ammonium 4,8-dioxa-3H-perfluorononanoate	958445-44-8	3.09	-3.01	24.10	-2.01	5.53	7.54	5.44	80.92	-5.66
60	3-perfluoro-methoxypropanoic acid	377-73-1	3.94	-1.07	3.30	-2.88	3.92	6.79	3.85	31.67	-3.93
61	perfluoro-4-methoxybutanoic acid	863090-89-5	3.47	-1.43	2.10	-3.07	4.79	7.86	4.71	41.41	-3.62
62	3,3,4,4,5,5,6,6,6-nonafluorohexan-1-ol	2043-47-2	2.94	-1.55	0.87	-3.45	4.75	8.20	4.67	57.31	3.85
63	3,3,4,4,5,5,6,6,7,7,8,8,8-tridecafluorooctan-1-ol	647-42-7	1.96	-2.93	1.61	-3.19	6.12	9.31	6.02	80.68	2.00
64	3,3,4,4,5,5,6,6,7,7,8,8,9,9,10,10,10-heptafluorodecan-1-ol	678-39-7	0.98	-3.92	1.28	-3.29	7.39	10.68	7.27	102.81	2.34
65	2:2 fluorotelomer alcohol	54949-74-5	4.02	-0.38	1.15	-3.33	3.19	6.53	3.14	26.40	3.70
66	4,8-dioxa-3H-perfluorononanoic acid	919005-14-4	2.97	-2.43	5.01	-2.69	5.51	8.21	5.42	52.96	-1.64
67	12:2 fluorotelomer alcohol	39239-77-5	-1.49	-5.75	0.20	-4.09	10.17	14.26	10.00	147.72	2.96
68	6:2 fluorotelomer sulfonamide aminoxide	80475-32-7	2.43	-5.05	423.89	-0.77	6.28	7.05	6.17	142.42	-1.46
69	6:2 fluorotelomer sulfonamide alkylbetanin	34455-29-3	2.58	-5.31	1017.75	-0.39	6.30	6.69	6.19	146.62	-0.69
70	perfluoro-2-methoxyacetic acid	674-13-5	4.55	-0.50	4.64	-2.73	3.33	6.06	3.27	19.94	-7.61

Table 4 : Estimated environmental endpoints for 71 PFAS defined for the analysis in the PROMISCES project (cont.)

ID	Name	CAS	Sw [log mg/L]	VP [log mmHg]	k _H [mol · Pa ⁻¹ · m ⁻³]	LogK _{AW}	LogK _{OW}	LogK _{OA}	LogK _{OC}	MP [°C]	BCF
71	3,3,4,4,5,5,6,6,7,7,8,8,9,9,10,10,11,11,12,12,12-henicosafuorododecan-1-ol	865-86-1	-0.14	-5.12	1.28	-3.29	8.70	11.99	8.56	125.06	1.94

Values in black indicated predictions within AD of the models. The red font next to the compound indicates that it was outside the model AD and the value may differ from the actual value. Blue values indicate that predictions are extrapolated and must be treated with caution.

2.2 Aquatic toxicity - General AI/ML-based aquatic toxicity model

Aquatic toxicity is being investigated for a broad range of aquatic organisms. During the modelling, the focus is on LC50 (lethal concentration affecting 50% of the population) and NOEC (no observed effect level) as a surrogate for acute and chronic toxicity, respectively. In addition, EC50-values (concentration affecting 50% of the population by one way or the other, except for mortality) are included in the database. For the modelling approach, we first applied ML to develop a model based on a broad range of organic chemicals, including PFAS. This general model was analyzed on its predictive performance for PFAS specifically, and only if necessary a PFAS specific model will be developed. The general hypothesis is that the model will learn the essential patterns and can use these patterns on the broader universe of chemicals (i.e. transfer learning) for the prediction of aquatic toxicity for PFAS chemicals.

2.2.1 Data collection and data curation

The ECETOC database was used as the starting point for model development. This database contains a suite of data on the aquatic toxicity of mostly organic chemicals for a variety of endpoints ranging from impacts on hatching up till mortality. Thereupon, data on different test durations (chronic as well as acute toxicity) and on different aquatic species of different trophic levels (varying from for instance algae to fish) are included. Following a detailed data curation procedure, a list of chemicals, species, and exposure durations was obtained (Table 5). Curation steps included amongst others the focus on ‘aquatic species’, ‘laboratory experiments’, ‘aquatic exposure’ (no injection, oral exposure), and ‘LC50, EC50, and NOEC’. In addition, general data cleaning took place, like curation of chemical structures, removing incomplete entries, and removing unrealistic values etc. This data was enriched with several other types of information/descriptors (Table 6).

Table 5: Information on the curated dataset.

	Number of measurements	Number of unique biological species	Number of unique chemicals
Total	67197	1310	2702
LC50	52262		
EC50	3034		
NOEC	11901	84	869

Table 6: Information on the descriptors that have been used for the modelling phase.

Category of descriptors	Specification
Chemical	Chemical fingerprint Phys-chem properties Mode of action
Species	Species similarity
Exposure duration	Harmonized duration acute Harmonized duration chronic
Experimental	Experimental setting Media type
Endpoint	Type of endpoint (LC50, NOEC) Type of effect

2.2.2 AI/ML-based modelling

This activity focussed on the modelling activities that take account of the limited number of toxicity data typically available for PFAS compounds. One of the key issues in this respect is to use the data as efficiently as possible, and also to use information on other classes of compounds as efficiently as possible. For the latter purpose, the merits of transfer learning were exploited in the reporting period. By far most data are available on PFAO and PFOS – it is therefore essential to use the scarcely available information on other PFAS compounds as efficiently as possible.

The first step in AI/ML-based modelling was the development and validation of a classification as well as a quantification model for the prediction of aquatic toxicity of organic compounds in general, including PFAS chemicals. The classification model is suited to classify PFAS compounds in a set of toxicity classes in line with the requirements for classification and labelling within REACH. The initially developed quantitative ML model is able to predict the aquatic toxicity of PFAS compounds for different species. Amongst others, the options for species-species interpolation were exploited and it was specifically considered how in the future it can be demonstrated that models based on AI/ML approaches have an added value as compared to other in silico models. A manuscript has been accepted for publication¹⁸.

In addition to the initially developed model, we investigated the best-performing model using quantitative and qualitative transfer learning approaches (including Random forest and XGboost). This was done by using a set of algorithms and 10-fold Cross Validation (CV). The developed model (i.e. the initially developed model + transfer learning) predicted PFAS better after transfer learning, especially when equally weighting PFAS and non-PFAS to get better predictions for PFAS (Table 7). Limited improvement was achieved in this setting for non-PFAS.

Table 7: Model performance, expressed in terms of Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), on the transfer learning of PFAS.

Transfer learning (PFAS)	Substances (# chemicals included)	XGboost: all together	XGboost: equal weighting	XGboost: separate models
	non-PFAS (63396)	1,11	1,14	1,13
	PFAS (3801)	0,97	0,91	1,06

2.2.3 Model application

The final AI/ML-based model will be made publically available on GitHub. This model allows to generate predictions of effect levels for PFAS for any of the aquatic species for which toxicity data are available in the database used for model development. Options for endpoints include, as already mentioned, LC50-, EC50-, and NOEC-values.

Current efforts are focussing on improving the current models, not only with regard to reducing the RMSE, but also in qualitative performance. One of the options for model application that is currently processed is the application of model predictions in environmental risk assessment. The basic approach towards chemical risk assessment, for instance advocated in the REACH legislation, is to use toxicity data on different aquatic organisms to generate so-called species-sensitivity distributions (SSDs). The Maximum Permissible Concentration (MPC) for the environment is defined as the concentration which protects at least 95% of the species in an ecosystem, thereby protecting the functioning of the ecosystem. The MPC is also termed 'HC5' to indicate the Hazardous Concentration that affects 5% of the species. An SSD represents the cumulative frequency distribution of results of toxicity testing of individual species (Figure 1). As reflected in Figure 1, SSDs can be used retrospectively to derive

Environmental Quality Criteria (EQCs) as based on the common regulatory acceptance of 5 % of species potentially being at risk due to exposure to chemicals (HC5). In addition, the SSD concept allows the diagnostic assessment of the fraction of species potentially affected.

Figure 1: The species-sensitivity distribution (SSD) concept.

Each circle represents laboratory ecotoxicity data for a compound for a specific organism; (-) represents the fitted SSD. A potentially affected fraction of species (PAF) is derived from an ambient concentration x ($x \rightarrow y$). Environmental quality criteria (EQC) are derived from a chosen value of y ($y \rightarrow x$, here HC_5). HC_5 =hazardous concentration for 5% of the species. Redrawn from Posthuma et al.¹⁹.

Application of the models is foreseen to generate predictions of HC_5 -values for PFAS chemicals for which toxicity data are available, as well as for non-tested PFAS. This will, amongst others, allow for ranking PFAS chemicals according to their predicted toxicity. Subsequently, these predictions of HC_5 can for instance be used for identifying PFAS chemicals that are Safer by Design than currently commercialized PFAS chemicals. Examples of SSDs generated for a random set of PFAS chemicals are provided in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Examples of XGBoost SSDs for 10 randomly chosen PFAS chemicals.

3 Summary and conclusions

This deliverable provides a toolbox which is a summary of the *in silico* tools that were improved, newly developed, and adopted in the PROMISCES project for predicting the physicochemical properties and aquatic toxicity of PFAS.

In the case of physicochemical parameters needed for modeling fate, transport, and exposure of PFAS five Quantitative Structure-Property Relationship models were improved/developed/adopted.

Two QSPR models that were available in the literature (for water solubility, S_w) and vapor pressure, VP) were adopted and improved for the purpose of prediction of those endpoints for PFAS evaluated in PROMISCES.

Moreover, two completely new QSPR models to predict the octanol-water partition (K_{ow}) and bioconcentration factor (BCF) of PFAS were developed.

For the developing models for S_w , VP, and K_{ow} , in light of the lack of data availability, a new approach combining physics-based methods with data-driven models was proposed and applied.

The QSPR model for melting point (MP) that is available in literature, was evaluated in terms of the possibility of applying it for PFAS. This yielded a positive result and the QSPR model was therefore chosen as a model to predict MP for the compounds evaluated in PROMISCES.

All details of the improved/developed/adopted in PROMISCES *in silico* models for predicting the physicochemical properties of PFAS are presented in the standardized QMRF ((Q)SAR Model Reporting Format), and the used datasets and codes are uploaded to the Zenodo.

For estimation of other environmentally relevant endpoints required in fate and transport modeling, i.e. Henry's Law, $\log K_{AW}$, $\log K_{OA}$, and $\log K_{OC}$ further calculations were performed using appropriate mathematical transformations and predictions from the predictive models (S_w , VP, $\log K_{ow}$).

Predictions for all considered environmental endpoints for 71 PFAS defined for the analysis in the PROMISCES project were estimated and gathered.

The AI/ML-based model to predict the aquatic toxicity of organic compounds in general was developed and validated. The quantitative ML model is able to predict the aquatic toxicity of PFAS compounds for different species. The developed model predicted Perfluoroalkyl and Polyfluoroalkyl Substances (PFAS) better after transfer learning, especially when equally weighting PFAS and non-PFAS to get better predictions for PFAS.

The toolbox (collection of final QSPRs and AI/ML-based models) is publicly available on GitHub. This will allow users to generate predictions of the physicochemical properties of PFAS as well as effect levels for any of the aquatic species for which toxicity data are available in the database used for model development.

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